

EC Link Project 2015

Urban Renewal and Revitalization (URR)

Sustainability Lessons from
European Experiences

By Kosta Mathéy, PhD

Table of Contents

1. URBAN RENWAL AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	6
1.1. What is Urban Renewal?	6
1.2. Sustainable development through urban renewal	7
1.2.1. <i>Environmental Sustainability Objectives</i>	8
(A) <i>Climate Change Mitigation</i>	8
(B) <i>Climate Change Adaptation</i>	9
(C) <i>Ecological Sustainability</i>	10
(D) <i>Human Health concerns</i>	11
1.2.2. <i>Economic Sustainability Objectives</i>	11
1.2.3. <i>Social Sustainability</i>	12
2. THE EUROPEAN URBAN RENEWAL EXPERIENCE.....	15
2.1. Evolvment of European Urban Renewal Concepts.....	15
2.1.1. <i>1950-70 Post-War reconstruction</i>	15
2.1.2. <i>Modernization of older housing stock</i> (,rehabilitation') (1970→).....	16
2.1.3. <i>Cautious Urban renewal / preservation of listed buildings</i> (1978→).....	16
2.1.4. <i>Ecological Building and renewal</i> (1982→)	16
2.1.5. <i>Revalorization of large scale housing estates</i> (1984→ West /1990→ East)	17
2.1.6. <i>Social focus and target groups</i> (1995).....	18
2.1.7. <i>Sustainability projects</i> (2000→ MdG).....	18
2.1.8. <i>Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation</i> (2010→)	18
2.1.9. <i>,Smart' urban renewal</i> 2013→.....	19
3. THE ECO CITY TOOL BOX. Case Studies.....	21
3.1. Strategy: Environmental Sustainability through Climate Change Mitigation.....	21
3.1.1. <i>Objective: Reduction of Non-Renewable Energy Demand</i>	21
3.1.2. <i>Objective: Energy – Recycling</i>	25
3.1.3. <i>Objective: Clean and renewable energy</i>	27
3.1.4. <i>Objective: Land recycling, brown field redevelopment</i>	31
3.1.5. <i>Objective; Land reclamation</i>	32
3.2. Strategy: Environmental Sustainability through Climate Change Adaptation...33	
3.2.1. <i>Objective: Micro climate, / Heat island, reduction</i>	33

3.2.2.	<i>Objective: Flood protection</i>	35
3.2.3.	<i>Objective: Drought precaution</i>	39
3.2.4.	<i>Objective: Integrated flood prevention and erosion control</i>	41
3.3.	Strategy: Environmental sustainability	42
3.3.1.	<i>Objective: Combating resource depletion</i>	42
3.3.2.	<i>Objective: Preserving Biodiversity</i>	44
3.3.3.	<i>Objective: Healthy cities – healthy living</i>	48
3.3.4.	<i>Objective: Clean and fair building materials</i>	50
3.3.5.	<i>Objective: Air pollution control</i>	51
3.3.6.	<i>Objective: Noise pollution control</i>	54
3.4.	Strategy: Economic Sustainability	55
3.4.1.	<i>Objective: Public-private partnerships</i>	56
3.4.2.	<i>Objective: Green economy</i>	57
3.4.3.	<i>Objective: Economic revitalization and stronger global integration</i>	62
3.5	Strategy: Social Sustainability	71
3.5.1	<i>Objective: access to adequate shelter</i>	72
3.5.2	<i>Objective: Tackling the land question</i>	75
3.5.3	<i>Objective: Location and ease of mobility</i>	76
3.5.4	<i>Objective: Poverty alleviation</i>	83
3.5.5	<i>Objective: Social inclusion</i>	88
3.5.6	<i>Objective: Fighting stigmatization</i>	90
3.5.7	<i>Objective: Cultural identity</i>	93
3.5.8	<i>Objective: Crime and violence prevention</i>	96
3.5.9	<i>Objective: Conviviality, well being</i>	101
3.5.10	<i>Objective: Heritage conservation</i>	103
4	STANDARDS	105
4.1	Standards for the selection of renewal areas and beneficiaries	105
4.2	Standards for the protection of cultural heritage	105
4.3	Standards for energy conservation	108
4.4	Standards for ecological buildings	109
5	TECHNOLOGIES AND PRODUCTS	110
5.1	Energy saving for appliances	110
5.2	Passive energy conservation / Passive or Solar houses,	110
5.3	Active energy conservation	111
5.3.1	Zero energy house	111

5.3.2	<i>Energy Plus houses</i>	111
5.4	<i>Decentralized energy generation</i>	113
6	INDICATORS AND VERIFICATION METHODOLOGIES	114
6.1	<i>Criteria and Indicators for the selection of a renewal area:</i>	114
6.2	Indicators for success of renewal measures	115
7	SOME LESSONS LEARNT	115
7.1	Participation and PPP	115
7.2	Need for subsidies	115
7.3	Neighbourhood contracts	116
7.4	<i>Risk of gentrification and expulsion</i>	117

1. URBAN RENWAL AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Over the past 70 years, since the end of World War II, the urban development focus of most governments in the developing world—as well as that of most international aid agencies—has been on new construction. This is particularly true of development policy as it relates to residential areas, including those built through authorized channels as well as those that have emerged through informal processes rather than government initiative. Typically, most of this housing stock was constructed in a hurried manner.¹

Similarly, the desire for modernization by governments and decision makers in developing countries has often led to a view that only "modern" housing of new construction is a worthwhile investment. As a result, housing complexes of earlier vintage construction or those erected in the traditional style are often considered to be of little value. They are mostly torn down or, at best, ignored. Older-style housing, which is typically concentrated in the urban core, is often left in a state of physical deterioration and overcrowding, and tend to be poorly served by urban infrastructure. Therefore, it is easy to label such areas as "slums" and to slate them for demolition at the earliest opportunity.

Further, as a result of rapid population growth, many large cities in the developing world have undergone wholesale transformation of their urban economies, a phenomenon that has led to a dramatic shift in the composition of economic activity and the spatial pattern of land use in the urban core. The historic areas of such cities become transformed into tracts of land highly valued by commercial users. This increases the pressure to eliminate any remaining vintage housing stock.

1.1. What is Urban Renewal?

In recent years, urban renewal and revitalization (URR) have emerged as important issues in urban planning and design, mainly because of the economic, cultural, technological, and physical benefits it confers. In this context, "urban revitalization" refers to comprehensive reinvestment in the social, economic, cultural, and physical infrastructure of urbanized areas.

URR has been described as the intention to recover idle investment, employment, and consumption and to enhance the quality of life within urban areas.² Others have added "growth" and "progress" to the definition of what they refer to as "urban revitalization" and stated that, as with earlier labels (e.g., "urban redevelopment", and "urban regeneration") urban revitalization implies growth, progress, and infusion of new economic activities into stagnant or declining cities that are no longer attractive to investors or middle-class households.³

¹ This and the following paragraphs make reference to related work by Steinberg, F. 2008. *Revitalization of Historic Inner-city Areas in Asia: Urban renewal potentials in Jakarta, Hanoi and Manila*, Urban Development Series. Asian Development Bank. Manila.
<http://www.adb.org/Documents/Reports/revitalization-inner-city/Revitalization-Inner-City.pdf>

² Couch, C. 1990. *Urban Renewal: Theory and Practice*. London: Macmillan.

³ Holcomb, H. B., and R. A. Beauregard. 1981. *Revitalizing Cities*. Pennsylvania: Commercial Printing, Inc.

Ultimately, cities have always been in a state of progressive transition. They are in a continuous process of becoming larger, smaller, better, or worse—in one way or another, and different than they were in the past. This process of continuous transition occurs largely in response to the political, industrial, economic, and social changes. Decay of inner urban space often occurs within the context of such transformation. Inner urban decay, crime, racial tension, riots, mass unemployment, and falling standards in the provision of urban services are some of the more obvious and disturbing indicators of a general and deep-seated deterioration in the social, economic, political, and financial fabric of a city. It has been observed that such decline can lead to out-migration of younger and more skilled members of urban populations as they seek employment elsewhere.⁴

1.2. Sustainable development through urban renewal

Within the frameworks of sustainable development, which is considered an overriding principle for all future interventions in the environment since the 1992 UN Conference on Environment and Development, urban planning ideally should enable a fair balance between economic, social and environmental concerns.

The application of sustainable development principles are main characteristics of eco-cities.⁵ Hence, the fulfilment of eco-city requirements will be measured upon the satisfaction of the various sustainability objectives – which generally can be achieved in the combination of different reinforcing or complementary instruments or planning tools. Those will be explained to greater detail in the eco-city tool box further below.

⁴ Middleton, M. 1991. *Cities in Transition: The Regeneration of Britain's Inner Cities*. London: Michael Joseph.

⁵ Roseland, Mark (1997). "Dimensions of the Eco-city". *Cities* 14 (4): 197–202.

1.2.1. Environmental Sustainability Objectives

(A) Climate Change Mitigation

Climate change (including global warming) is currently one of the biggest threats to mankind. Modern urban development is one of its biggest causal factors. Hence, urban renewal has an important role to play in combating climate change. In such process, two different strategies need to be distinguished: **Mitigation** aims at reducing, stopping and eventually reversing climate change in the long run. The common logic of all mitigation strategies is to cut CO₂ emissions – mainly through stopping the use of non renewable energy resources. On the other hand, **Adaptation** strategies aim at reducing the vulnerability of human settlements against the effect of climate change.

Reduction of Non-Renewable Energy Demand

The argument is as simple as it is convincing: less combustion of non renewable energies (coal, petroleum, 'natural' gas) means less CO₂ emission which can stop global warming (by reducing the greenhouse effect)

Energy – Recycling

Recycling embodied energy in all kind of materials reduces the need for new generation of energy, but also energy transformation by means of heat exchangers, biogas plants, etc. Is equally beneficial for the environment

Clean and renewable energy

Not all energy sources impact directly on global climate. For example, biogas, wind or electricity generated through electro-voltaic can be considered clean energy which do not produce Green House Gas. The same applies to man-powered mobilization energy like cycling or walking.

Combined measures

More sophisticated measures ask for an interdisciplinary approach, like in the case of district heat-power plants (using waste energy in electricity production for heating purposes), or exploiting solar energy gains through house orientation, capturing of sun radiation energy or benefitting from night time cosmic cold radiation for cooling purposes.

Land recycling and brownfield redevelopment

As long as global population continue growing, additional land resources will be needed which invariably reduce the space for greens and natural forests which would have the capacity of transforming CO₂ into oxygen.

Land reclamation

Following the same logic, additionally needed land reserves can be created on shallow flood lands on swimming structures, palafites or traditional house boats. Some experts believe that water surfaces represent our most important 'land reserves' for the future.

(B) *Climate Change Adaptation*

Climate change mitigation efforts can only show visible results on the long run, if at all. Above all, they require simultaneous solidarity action by all nations, which so far has not materialized yet. In the meantime the most affected regions will have to bank on local defence mechanisms to secure their own survival (the so called adaptation strategy).

- Micro climate / heat island reduction

Cities tend to develop higher ambient temperatures than the countryside around them. This phenomenon is known as the 'heat island effect'. Combined with seasonal hot periods (heat waves), inner city temperatures may become insupportable for many and can be the cause of seasonally high death rates.

In addition, individual blocks or streets may show higher temperatures than the city average – typically due to lack of ventilation, heat absorbing wall and floor surfaces or lack of greenery. Air conditioning may improve the indoors situation but simultaneously worsens outdoors temperatures, and makes the poor, who cannot afford air conditioning, suffer for the well being of the rich.

- Flood protection

Possible flood hazards to cities may have different origins. In some regions, like the Amazon or South Asia they occur seasonally and are part of the habitual eco system, but occasionally turn out much stronger as usual – mostly accentuated through climate change -- and can cause serious disasters. Cities can protect themselves through only to limited extent, as their supplies depend on surrounding regions, and through which most of the transportation links to more distant places are also channelled. Other causes may include careless deforestation for agricultural purposes or the construction of dams and reservoirs in earthquake prone areas etc.

In coastal areas human settlements may be affected by the rise of sea water level due to the melting of ices around the globe's poles as a consequence of global warming. This is a slow but steady process but turns especially hazardous in combination of high tides and storms. If no other effective measures are found and taken those settlements would have to be abandoned in 10, 20 or 50 years.

- Drought prevention

When too much rain is falling in one region of the world it is no surprise that water is missing in others. Desertification has hit wide zones of Africa and Asia. But also in Europe water shortages occur more frequently than in the past. Water is an essential need for life and also the base for agricultural production. Rainwater catchment, recycling and simple water saving systems have become important requests in urban renewal projects around the globe.

- Disaster prevention and erosion control

Most, but not all environmental hazards are a direct consequence of climate change. Disasters, like tsunamis and earthquakes are examples; other are man-made like huge industrial accidents, fires, war damages all cause a need for urban reconstruction and renewal efforts in the aftermath – and for

provisions to reduce damages in case that a similar disaster should struck again.

(C) *Ecological Sustainability*

- Combating resource depletion

The fact that the mineral oil reserves will be exhausted in a few decades is perhaps good news in face of climate change and can be substituted by other kind of energy instead. But the planet possesses other essential resources which may be more difficult to replace, or need protection from all kind of pollution. Also land is becoming a scarce resource in urban development. Therefore urban reconstruction will have to be conscious of this fact in its own design, but also for its educative potential.

- Preserving Biodiversity

Species extinction is a natural part of Earth's history. Human activity has increased the extinction rate by at least 100 times compared to the natural rate.⁶ Paradoxically in Europe, which has undergone an important industrialization process in agriculture, urban areas nowadays count a higher diversity of species than the surrounding countryside. In urban renewal care must be taken to preserve, or even better: increase, this biodiversity.

⁶ http://www.google.de/imgres?imgurl=http://www.surfbirds.com/mb/media/living-planet-0207.jpg&imgrefurl=http://www.surfbirds.com/mb/Features/biodiversity-and-birds.html&h=350&w=500&tbnid=EvuoR50qeolcHM:&zoom=1&tbnh=90&tbnw=129&usq=nopLxHwT_8KtoEkhaMtp4ixK3tU=&docid=sUnwIhtAnbTGKM. Visited 10/07/2015

(D) *Human Health concerns*

- Healthy cities – healthy living

Mankind forms part of bio-diversity. Extinction is not an evident threat (though not impossible as a result of scientific or political mistake), but signs of degeneration cannot be denied. The built environment and urban lifestyles play a considerable part in this development, but are difficult to control by the individual. This is what the concern for WHO-supported Healthy Cities network⁷ is all about. In Scotland⁸, but also other parts of Europe, Healthy City concerns have become an integral part of urban renewal strategies.

- Clean and fair building materials

The science of Building Biology provides an interesting theoretical reference framework also for urban renewal projects world-wide. But particularly important in the context of energy conservation in urban renewal initiatives is the embodied portion of CO₂ in the building materials consumed.

- Air pollution control

Many cities which do not happen to be located in a windy location suffer from smog these days – with serious consequences for public health and quality of life. Smog control has therefore become an important secondary goal of urban renewal projects in many places.

- Noise pollution control

Equally disturbing can be noise pollution in cities. Most urban renewal projects, consciously or not, result in lower noise emissions locally.

1.2.2. Economic Sustainability Objectives

By today all planners and architects should have understood that no urban renewal plan will be implemented if the financial aspects have been worked out and settled beforehand. Economic sustainability means that both investment costs and operational expenses have been calculated and the financial sources been identified and confirmed. This does not necessarily mean that each investment must be economically profitable, but any subsidies must be justified by its social, ecological or similar value.

- Green economy / Green Finance / Local Currency

The term **green economy** often only refers to low or non-carbon industries which may require some temporary financial regulation mechanisms to keep CO₂-free production competitive with conventional products and services.⁹

Green Finance investment schemes are set up (especially in Britain) to spread the higher investment cost of low-carbon production or consumption over a longer period and to offset them against long term savings. UNEP, however, also includes other sustainability factors in the Green economy concept: *‘UNEP has developed a working definition of a green economy as one that results in improved human well-being and social equity, while signif-*

⁷ <http://www.euro.who.int/en/health-topics/environment-and-health/urban-health/activities/healthy-cities/who-european-healthy-cities-network> accessed 10/07/2015

⁸ <http://www.sphsu.mrc.ac.uk/Evidence/Research/Review%2009/Slides09.pdf> visited 10/07/2015

⁹ <http://climatepolicyinitiative.org/interactive/moving-to-a-low-carbon-economy/index.html?gclid=C1zhsoHP0cYCFUcTwwodEHcEMA>, viewed 11/07/2015

*icantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities. In its simplest expression, a green economy can be thought of as one which is low carbon, resource efficient and socially inclusive.*¹⁰ According to this interpretation, local solidarity economies and even local currency are being considered to offer more sustainable economic undertakings in contrast to profit maximising economies.

The establishment of green economy enterprises tend to work best in clusters, which hints to the need for shared infrastructure provision. Sometimes such clusters are integrated in brown field redevelopment projects.

- Employment and Income generation

A major proportion of urban revitalization programs are being proposed for zones in which an important local employer has folded down or where there is a concentration of unemployed residents for other reasons. In consequence, the creation of new employment becomes a central objective of such projects, aiming at fixing the root problem of such areas and securing sustainability to the venture.

- Reduced cost of infrastructure

Compared to new green field development, urban renewal can turn out to be more economical if existing infrastructure (roads, sewers etc.) can be integrated. Also for residents the possibility to remain in the same neighbourhood tends to be highly beneficial, since transportation cost from most likely less central locations can be spared and residential communities are not torn apart.

- Internationalization

In the light of Globalization, many urban renewal initiatives are conceived like a shop window towards the world and expected to facilitate an upward move on the World Cities scale.¹¹

1.2.3. Social Sustainability

Since physical decay of urban quarters can be interpreted as being not more than a symptom of other social and economic difficulties, an intelligent urban renewal program will try to analyse and cure the roots of the observed problematic. Most likely, as a result the envisaged measures will try to tackle the physical symptoms together with their social (and possibly economic) roots.

- Location and ease of mobility

The greater a city, the more important becomes the aspect of accessibility of both residential areas and commercial zones. By definition urban renewal as a preferential alternative to green field development aims at preserving the established accessibility qualities of a neighbourhood given by its location. But many renewal projects additionally include an improvement in mobility opportunities – either by providing car parking facilities or allowing for reserved circulation space for pedestrians and cyclists.

¹⁰ <http://www.unep.org/greeneconomy/> viewed 11/07/2015;

<http://www.unep.org/greeneconomy/AboutGEI/WhatIsGEI/tabid/29784/Default.aspx> viewed 11/07/2015

¹¹ <http://www.lboro.ac.uk/gawc/> reviewed 11/07/2015

- Sufficient and good quality of housing

Due to a typically aged physical texture of renewal zones, building structures tend to be deficient which attracts a certain share of low- and least-income sections of society and who often bring with them the problem of overcrowding in addition. Therefore houses (residential or commercial) tend to require considerable repair and modernization. In addition, densification or overspill areas may become an additional necessity.
- Responding to demographic change

Family structures have changed over time – today there are more single households and the population is getting older. Migration results in greater cultural diversity but also bears the danger of ethnic conflicts. Not only dwelling sizes need to be adjusted but specialized infrastructure support may be needed – and sometimes provided within urban renewal or revitalization schemes like in the German case study on the ‘Social City’ (chapter 3.5.4).
- Poverty reduction, education & skills

Well-to-do neighbourhoods dispose of the necessary economic means to keep their living environment in good shape. On the other hand, those quarters of the city earmarked for urban renewal programs tend to display problems of poverty and limited educational skills which must be addressed in one way or another in the interest of sustainability in the achievements of the program in question.
- Social inclusion.

Several European renewal programs attempt to overcome the observed stigmatization of run-down urban quarters through improving the social mix or the physical appearance of public space. Sometimes mixing residents with different social backgrounds has been attempted to promote inclusion, but more often than not failed-especially where the mix was enforced from outside. The case study on South Rotterdam (Chapter 3.5.6) shows a positive example where ‘higher standard’ residents were given incentives to move into poorer neighbourhoods.
- Cultural identity.

Whereby social exclusion is related to the view by outsiders, reinforcing cultural identity of a neighbourhood is primarily meant to raise the self-esteem of the residents themselves and support mutual aid initiatives. These may be monument of a local hero, physical landmarks, a traditional market or even an old and huge tree on a square. If no historical or popular piece of identification is at hand, a new ‘iconic building’ (or even an invented old one) can be constructed like in the Case of Bilbao (Case study chapter 3.4.3)
- Conviviality, well being, image improvement

Irrespective of the social status of the residents, almost all urban renewal programs try to raise the living standards and especially outdoors environmental qualities. Parks, urban forests, beaches, pedestrian streets could stand for examples.

- Crime and Violence prevention

Urban crime and violence are on the increase in many parts of the world, and counter measures are usually welcome by residents and politicians. *Crime Prevention through Environmental Design* (CPTED) theories enjoy, possibly unjustified, high popularity and are, by definition, urban valorisation programs.

2. THE EUROPEAN URBAN RENEWAL EXPERIENCE

Many urban renewal projects have been planned, executed and somehow concluded around the world. However, this document we will restrict itself to the European context, where the richest spectrum of urban renewal projects can be found. Certainly, transferability of European project experiences to China is limited, but most of the tools are generic and can be adapted to serve different objectives and, above all, to different settings.

2.1. Evolvement of European Urban Renewal Concepts

In Europe, as everywhere else on the Globe, urban renewal in significant numbers and size is post-World War II history. Different programs have been consecutively developed over the past 70 years – following changing needs (and objectives), strategies, policies and political ideologies or prejudices. A policy overview of European experience will hence be presented by periods:

2.1.1. 1950-70 Post-War reconstruction

More than any other war before, World War II targeted the civil population and city-based industries of the enemy countries. Especially in Germany, but also in its enemy countries, important parts of urban texture were completely destroyed by air raids. When the war was over, large scale urban renewal turned to more or less provisional repair of damaged buildings, but otherwise massive reconstruction mostly on the existing block pattern in order to take advantage of remaining infrastructure and also to avoid solving any ownership queries.

Particularly interesting is the subsidized West German social housing reconstruction program, which combined affordable housing for all and simultaneously fuelled the post-war economy – which later on became known as the ‘German Economy Miracle’ (*Wirtschaftswunder*)

2.1.2. **Modernization of older housing stock** (,rehabilitation') (1970→)

Once the post-war housing deficit was resolved there remained a quality contrast between the modern new built housing units and the repaired pre-war stock -- especially in the urban periphery and in smaller towns who had been less hit during the war. Special modernization subsidies were made available to individually modernize the existing buildings

2.1.3. **Cautious Urban renewal / preservation of listed buildings** (1978→)

Now that a strong construction industry had been built up, a massive drop in orders would have caused a serious recession and possibly also caused social unrest. The strategic answer was the creation of a nation-wide area-based participatory urban renewal program which also extended to the public space and to smaller villages. Apart from a specially created subsidy line, further interest in the program was fuelled by a recurring national competition for the most beautiful village. The reconstruction of historic monuments of that period followed more a concept of open air museums.

2.1.4. **Ecological Building and renewal** (1982→)

The idea of building ecologically began to spread in Europe from the early 1980's onwards. Although the first global energy crisis of 1973 had been overcome in the meantime, the importance of natural and local resource preservation had been understood, but practical implementation of the principles depended on private initiative and the academic *avant-garde*. Due to technocratic building regulations new 'ecological' buildings were difficult to erect inside urban centres, where the reconstruction of traditional timber frame and even mud buildings could occasionally be seen.

<p><i>Bathroom in mud building, Kassel, Germany. Architect and photo: G.Minke.</i> https://www.google.com/search?newwindow=1&site=imghp&tbn=isch&source=hp&biw=1067&bih=539&q=lehmhaus+minke&oq=lehmhaus+minke&gs_l=img.3...297691.302594.2.303697.8.6.1.1.0.0.120.570.5j1.6.0...0...1ac.1.64.img..3.13.1104.NTOxuASTziY#imgrc=_</p>		

A parallel but relatively independent movement of the period was the concept of 'biological construction' – a synonym of today's healthy building and healthy cities concept.

2.1.5. Revalorization of large scale housing estates (1984→ West /1990→ East)

Like elsewhere on the world, East and West Europe had experienced a hype in industrialized building – especially large panel construction for social housing from the late 1960*s onwards. With the spread of neoliberal politics in Europe social housing became a service not for all anymore but an assistance exclusively to the poor, which damaged the connotations of this building typology. Unresolved building physics and maintenance problems, plus building failures after 20 years of intensive use triggered off comprehensive renewal programs of those settlements from the mid 1980s onwards. In Germany after reunification 1990, massive renewal and de-densification programs were begun, including also partial or full demolition in response to marked demand and population loss.

<p>La Duchiere in Lyon (France) was one of the first and with its 5,500 dwellings probably also the biggest social housing estate built in the 1960s. It was renovated 2011.13. Source:</p>	<p>Large housing estate after demolition of upper floors in Leinefelde, Eastern Germany Source: http://www.baunetzwissen.de</p>

http://lyonnews.com/uploads/Une_zone_de_securite_prioritaire_a_La_Duchere_pour_mieux_reprimer_la_delinquance_de_ce_quartier_1346671516.jpg	
---	--

2.1.6. Social focus and target groups (1995)

Globalization widened the gap between the rich and the poor also in Europe during the 1990s, and area based social assistance programs replaced the former programs more focussing on physical improvement. This tendency to earmark neighbourhoods with special assistance needs is a global phenomenon, has brought about a number of good results but also bears the risk of area stigmatization.

2.1.7. Sustainability projects (2000→ MdG)

The year 2000 brought us the *millennium development goals* for sustainability which should be achieved by 2015, but were recently reformulated as Sustainable Development Goals to be attained in a follow-up period after 2015. As not unusual in politics, this may not necessarily stipulate new and more intense efforts but may turn into a mere re-labelling of ongoing programs now promoted to be 'sustainable projects' with no fundamental changes.

2.1.8. Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation (2010→)

Since 1992 United Nations Climate Change Conferences have been held on a yearly basis, The 2009 Conference agreed on the Copenhagen Protocol, which was signed by 141 member states and set the aim to limit global warming to 2°C by 2010. It was also agreed that the industrialized countries should assist the poorer regions to obtain the necessary capacity for doing so by means of technology transfer. Although the commitment to the goals remained voluntary, the agreement at least provided large scale publicity about the problematic situation among politicians which filtered down to the

level of urban renewal programs. Many programs set the reduction of CO₂ emission as the top objective.

<p>A chart from the U.N.'s latest climate report shows the planet's rising temperatures from 1901 to 2012.</p> <p>Source: foxnews.com. http://a57.foxnews.com/global.fncstatic.com/static/managed/img/Scitech/876/493/Global%20warming%20trends%20IPCC%202013%20AR5.jpg?ve=1&t=1, viewed 12/07/2015</p>	<p>Mazdar City in Abu Dhabi</p> <p>Source: Azimuth Project, http://math.ucr.edu/home/baez/diary/masdar.jpg</p>

2.1.9. „Smart“ urban renewal 2013→

The call for technology transfer, combined with the request for private sector initiatives, was eagerly taken up by international companies such as Cisco, Siemens or Mercedes to promote the Smart City concept all over the world, and especially in context with urban (re)development.¹² The promise tells us that with the help of digital information technology an optimization of all urban activities it will be possible to minimize urban energy demand and that the internet will facilitate democratic decision making. However, the globally best publicised smart city project, Mazdar City in Abu Dhabi has not advanced as intended and the stories told by visitors don't sound very enthusiastic.

¹² http://www.siemens.de/topics/de/de/nachhaltige-stadtentwicklung/Pages/home.aspx?stc=wwcg102070&s_kwcid=AL!462!3!69003630255!p!!g!!smart%20city&ef_id=VYrt5gAABHLYgglk:20150712185457:s, viewed 12/07/2015

STRATEGIES FOR URBAN UPGRADING PROGRAMS

2. Climate Change Adaptation
Micro climate / Heat island reduction
Flood protection
Drought prevention
Disaster prevention and erosion control

1. Climate Change Mitigation (Reduction of CO ₂ Emissions)
Reduction of Non-Renewable Energy Demand
Energy – Recycling
Clean and renewable energy

5. Social Sustainability
Multiple social / policies
Sufficient and good quality housing
Demographic change (ageing, migration and mobility);
Poverty reduction
Educational & skills
Social inclusion
Cultural identity
Image improvement
Conviviality, well being
Crime and violence prevention

4. Economic Sustainability
Green economy
Green Finance
Income generation effects, employment
Cost of infrastructure
Building and maintenance cost control (also includes financing costs)
Cost recovery

3. Ecological Sustainability
Combating resource depletion
Preserving Biodiversity
Healthy cities – healthy living
Air pollution control
Noise pollution control

2

3. THE ECO CITY TOOL BOX. Case Studies of Applied Eco-City Tools in Europe:

In the following chapters we will portray specific *tools* and *instruments* which have been introduced in Europe in the recent past and which had been developed specifically *to attain the urban renewal objectives* listed in the previous section. *Examples* of their practical application are given in the context of brief and illustrated *Case Studies from Europe*. Furthermore internet links lead to more comprehensive documentation of the reference cases for further information.

3.1.Strategy: Environmental Sustainability through Climate Change Mitigation

Given the overall Objective has been identified as stopping Global Warming, different strategies can be followed. The first one to be covered here is C.C. mitigation. Each strategy has its own set of objectives.

3.1.1. Objective: Reduction of Non-Renewable Energy Demand

TOOL: Thermal roof insulation by adding extra floor

The most common tool for CO₂ reduction in Europe consists in improving the thermal insulation of walls and roofs of old buildings (saving non renewable fuel). In order to avoid condensation of moisture within the walls the insulation is normally fixed on the outside of the building skin. In historic buildings with facing bricks or decorated facades special techniques, like the incorporation of a moisture barrier or a thick layer of light mud plaster allow to place the insulation on the inner side of the wall construction.

Case Study: Copenhagen: Ryesgade 2012¹³

This listed building in central Copenhagen was poorly insulated and needed to improve its thermal performance. Since this measure required a new roof anyway, the addition of a supplementary floor incorporated the additional roof insulation, provided the finance for the remainder insulation and allowed densification of land use at the same time. In addition, photovoltaic panels alone, fixed on the penthouse roof, reduced energy demand by 5%. All together, the energy demand of this property could be reduced by 73% through the combination of different measures.

Copenhagen Ryesgade. Photo: Carsten Ingemann (same website as text reference DAC- Cities)

Case Study: Berlin 'Am Urban' 2012.¹⁴

In a Berlin traditional working-class Quarter, Kreuzberg, an old hospital dating from the 19th century became out of use and was replaced by a modern concrete monster nearby. The vacant old and obsolete buildings, now protected as listed buildings, were bought by an initiative of local residents who redeveloped it as a car-free residential community. All buildings were completely remodelled in line with the residents' preferences and well insulated with the assistance by the government subsidy program for energy saving housing construction.¹⁵ To preserve the appearance of the facing-brick facade, internal insulation was provided through a 10cm layer of light mud mortar which does not require a –usually unreliable – damp proof insulation, At the same time the risks were avoided of common polystyrene insulation material which had caused 17 death victims in the 1996 Düsseldorf airport fire in 1996.¹⁶

¹³ <http://www.dac.dk/en/dac-cities/sustainable-cities/all-cases/buildings/copenhagen-renovation-has-reduced-energy-consumption-by-73-in-ryesgade/> viewed 13/07/2015

¹⁴ https://www.umweltbank.de/kredit/index_kreditbeispiel_40.html seen 22/08/2015

¹⁵ https://www.nachhaltigkeitspreis.de/app/uploads/2014/09/DNP2014_Kurzbegruendung_Am_Urban.pdf seen 22/08/2015

¹⁶

<http://www.google.de/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=7&ved=0CEAQFjAGahUKEwjS587xhNnGA-hUEKXIKHebSAec&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.nfpa.org%2F~%2Fmedia%2Ffiles%2Fresearch%2Ffire%2520investigations%2Fdusseldorf.ashx&ei=2yukVZKOFYTSyAPmpYe4Dg&usq=AFQjCNHI7vKpHtjibmUna45wOe0TfL7LNq&bvm=bv.97653015.d.bGQ>, visited 13/07/2015

<p><i>Berlin: Light mud plaster for insulation, Am Urban</i></p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Photo: Kosta Mathéy</i></p>	<p><i>Berlin: Listed Building Am Urban</i></p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Photo: Kosta Mathéy</i></p>

TOOL: High tech energy refurbishing

Theoretically, a high-tech combination of insulating the building skin with other climate active measures, such as solar collectors, electro-voltaic cells, heat pumps, grey water recycling, green facades or roofs, can make the difference between a zero-energy house and an energy-plus building.

Case Study: France; Eco-Quartiers, Grenoble 2009^{17, 18, 19}

Obviously, true and comprehensive energy saving and ecological urban development cannot be developed on an individual site. Therefore, The French ministry of Ecology called for a competition between cities to build an Eco Quarter – which was won by the city of Grenoble in 2009. In this inner city brown field redevelopment scheme the 8.5 hectare site of former military barracks was redeveloped into a compound comprising 850 flats, student residences, a school, cinema and shopping units. All buildings had either green roofs or photovoltaic cells and solar collectors to satisfy 50% of the hot water demand; all building materials were 100% ecology proof. However, after occupation it turned out that the estimated energy demand of (42.5 kWh/m²/year) was overrun by 5 to 70%, most likely due to wrong calculations at the outset.

In 2011, there was a second call in the French Eco-Cities program, which was won for the **Plateau de Haye**²⁰ next to Nancy, where 14.600 people found new homes in a 440 ha redevelopment project. Apart from the obvious measures to reduce carbon dioxide emission (certified low energy buildings, gas-timber heating, car-sharing, bicycle lanes, reinforced public transport, community gardens) also social sustainability was sought through participatory democracy rules, mixed land uses, community building activities) and similar efforts.

¹⁷ http://www.lemonde.fr/planete/article/2011/11/09/a-grenoble-les-rates-du-premier-ecoquartier-francais_1601064_3244.html visited 02/06/2015

¹⁸ http://www.dailymotion.com/video/xb6z8t_ecoquartier-de-la-zac-de-bonne-a-gr_news

¹⁹ <http://eco-quartiers.fr/#!/fr/espace-infos/etudes-de-cas/zac-de-bonne-1/> visited 02/06/2015

²⁰ http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/DP_EcoQuartier_-_partie_3.pdf visited 02/06/2015

<p><i>Grenoble, Eco Quartier ZAC de Bonne</i></p> <p>Source: http://www.placegrenet.fr/wp-content/uploads/2013/06/Bepos-Zac-Bonne.jpg?d1dac0</p>	<p>Nancy. Plateau de Haye. 2014</p> <p>Source. http://projets-architecte-urbanisme.fr/images-archi/2011/12/ecoquartier-union.jpg</p>

TOOL: Stakeholder participation through social media and the internet

Stakeholder participation is a mandatory practice in sustainable green politics and works best in communities small enough for everybody to know each other. Participation becomes a challenge when communities grow bigger up to the size of a city quarter or even a metropolis. A feasible practice is to involve social media and the internet in order to reach such large numbers of stakeholders.

Case Study: Bristol European Green Capital 2015^{21, 22}

The city of Bristol in Southwest England, which is currently known to be the greenest city in the United Kingdom, has developed an innovative approach to sustainable urban development and citizen involvement. Some of its success relies on making use of the social media and interactive websites and involving residents and local companies in the city's green development.²³ For example, Bristol has organized *live lab conferences*²⁴ via social media and interactive websites in conjunction with George Ferguson's (Mayor of Bristol for Architecture)²⁵ idea to make the city a "Laboratory for Change". The conferences invited Bristol residents to participate actively in the city's development. A *You Tube Video*²⁶ was produced where locals were stopped in the street and were thanked for their efforts with a song.

*Future Bristol*²⁷ is one among many interactive websites, which will encourage people to get involved and to understand what it means to be a

²¹ <http://www.dac.dk/en/dac-cities/sustainable-cities/all-cases/social-city/bristol-involves-citizens-in-sustainable-urban-development/> viewed 30/05/2015

²² <https://www.bristol2015.co.uk/> viewed 30/05/2015

²³ www.BristolGreenCapital.org, visited 16/07/2015.

²⁴ <https://www.at-bristol.org.uk/livelabforschools.html> visited 22/08/2015

²⁵ <http://www.bristol.gov.uk/page/george-ferguson-mayor-bristol> seen 22/08/2015

²⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wa7oCBnTYS0> viewed 30/05/2015

²⁷ <http://www.futurebristol.co.uk/> visited 16/07/2015

"low carbon city" resident. The site provides an opportunity to vote for or against potential projects in the city. This will give a picture of what solutions the people of Bristol would like to see in the future.

During Bristol's [BIG Green Week](http://biggreenweek.com/)²⁸ car traffic is completely blocked from the city centre. [Bristol Green Doors](http://www.bristolgreendoors.org/)²⁹ is an event, in which everyone interested is invited to visit private homes, which were built in accordance with environmental standards or which contain green and sustainable solutions.

In addition, Bristol is well advanced in terms of reducing air and sound pollution, energy planning, waste separation and a green transport network, which includes CO₂-free hydrogen boats.

3.1.2. **Objective: Energy – Recycling**

Since energy recycling is one of three basic principles of energy saving (avoiding, recycling, clean production), many different variations of applications exist and one or another tool is incorporated in most case studies.

TOOL: Reuse of embodied energy

Within the scope and duration of an urban renewal process the embodied energy of any existing constructions is best recovered by adapting, modernizing or transforming the same rather than demolishing and replacing them.

After completion of the renewal works and during the subsequent utilization period recycling of embodied energy requires the (previous or/and posterior) separation and controlled removal of household and other waste – which at least requires adequate storage and transportation facilities. In Europe this process is standard practice in most municipalities and large variety of technologies are in use.

TOOL: Heat exchangers

²⁸ <http://biggreenweek.com/> seen 30/05/2015

²⁹ <http://www.bristolgreendoors.org/> seen 30/05/2015

Where the regional climate requires heating or cooling of indoor living space, much energy is lost during the necessary exchange of used air for fresh air. However, direct exchange of heat (or cold) between two air streams is relative simple by use of heat exchangers in which both air streams are separated through a membrane over a larger area. Commercial heat exchangers can recover 70% of the heat normally lost through necessary room ventilation.³⁰ The same principle can also be applied for warm water but only makes sense where larger quantities of hot water are being consumed – like saunas, swimming pools, canteen kitchens etc.

<p>Heat exchanger system.</p> <p>Source: http://www.homepower.com/sites/default/files/styles/article_gallery_active/public/articles/images/Core_Airflow.jpg?itok=0PsO0hsz, seen 15/07/2015</p>	<p>Heat exchanger detail</p> <p>Source: http://www.homepower.com/articles/home-efficiency/equipment-products/heat-energy-recovery-ventilators</p>

TOOL: Capturing biogas of organic waste

Biogas is produced in de fermentation of organic material. It contains methane, a potent greenhouse gas with a warming effect that is 21 times greater than that produced by carbon dioxide.³¹ When biogas is burnt it still releases CO₂, but with much less impact on global warming which can even be neutralized in production of new organic matter. Therefore, it is a good idea to capture and use the biogas which is generated in the context of urban greening and organic waste collection – for example in a local heat-energy plant within an urban eco-block as part of an urban or brown field renewal project.

³⁰ <http://www.homepower.com/articles/home-efficiency/equipment-products/heat-energy-recovery-ventilators> seen 15/07/2015

³¹ <http://www.tusk.org/userfiles/file/PACE/science-sample/Biogas%20and%20Climate%20Change.pdf> seen 15/07/2015

3.1.3. Objective: Clean and renewable energy

Quantitative reduction of energy consumption is a virtue in the context of oil-based economies, but energy in itself is not a bad thing. After all, life is energy and nothing else. And in fact, the term 'renewable energy' is misleading since even crude oil is renewable – but the cycle length takes several million years and we have to deal with the short-term effects of over consumption, to which our ecosystem, and even less our human organisms, may be unable to adapt. Therefore, to enable mankind to survive, we must take care and stop or even better: reverse the phenomenon of climate change. Stopping CO₂ emissions is the most significant single measure to achieve this aim.

TOOL: Autonomous energy supply

Electric power is highly versatile but suffers from the high energy losses connected to generation technology and to the resistance of transmission cables and transformers. Many factors are involved but as a general figure we can assume that less than 30% of the originally inserted energy reaches the consumer.³² Therefore it makes a lot of sense to decentralize power production and furthermore to capture the unavoidable electricity energy losses in the form of heat (a conventional light bulb only transforms 1% into light but 99% into heat!). Decentralized energy production also has the charm that it can be mostly powered through renewable energy sources such as photovoltaic cells, wind power generators, small hydroelectric generators and, last but not least, conventional water solar collectors.

Many urban renewal and revitalization projects in Europe include local energy production whether on the house/dwelling unit or on a district level,

³² <https://electricalnotes.wordpress.com/2013/07/01/total-losses-in-power-distribution-transmission-lines-part-1/>. Visited 15/07/2015

Case Study: Graz public - private partnership programme ECOPROFIT, 1990

The city of Graz with about 250.000 inhabitants is situated in a basin shape topography. At the same time Graz is an important industrial area. The combination of these two conditions, associated with inversion weather, used to cause heavy smog especially in winter. Smog is partly caused by excessive burning of non-renewable energy and therefore, in 1989, the municipality decided that it was time for a change and started an initiative to 'purify' industrial energy use within the city. A public - private partnership programme was born and given the name ECOPROFIT. The objectives of the program was to reduce emissions and increase resource efficiency through measures inside the companies - permitting cost savings in the production line as well as achieving the Kyoto environmental targets.³³

Since both, smog and high energy consumption directly relate to efficiency of production processes, the municipality's central strategy was to convince the private sector companies to invest in cleaner energies and in energy savings. In fact, the Graz experience shows that 50% of those investments have amortized in less than 2 years!

The extraordinary success of the ECO PROFIT program already convinced more than 60 cities to adopt the program for their own purposes – involving more than 1000 companies.

<p>UNU - Zero Emission Approach</p> <p>M. Suzuki, UNU</p>	
<p>The UNU Zero Emission Approach in the ECO PROFIT program Source: http://www.tf.uns.ac.rs/tempusIV/documents/presentations/04/GE-10-2010-04_Retraining_Industrial_%20MFM.pdf, visited 16/07/2015</p>	<p>Local Streetcar is advertising the ECOPROFIT private sector partners. Source: https://www.google.com/search?newwindow=1&biw=1067&bih=539&site=imghp&tbn=isch&sa=1&q=%C3%B6koprofit+graz&oeq=%C3%B6koprofit+graz&gs_l=img...12...2524.3058.0.6201.2.2.0.0.0.103.198.1j1.2.0....0...1c.1.64.img..2.0.0.xcJ7zFpFiJ0#imgrc=IOvPiHNYfslX8M%3A</p>

³³ <http://ec.europ> The project that were experienced over 10 years in Graz: 105 companies of 38 different branches that participated within the last 10 years achieved cost savings of 22 Million Euro and an economical growth up to 15% per year with municipal assistance of about 1.5 Million Euro and own efforts of about 0.75Million Euro. They reached a reduction of eco-related expenses for energy,water, waste, emissions' of partly about 70%.
a.eu/clima/policies/g-gas/kyoto/index_en.htm seen 15/07/2015

2nd Case Study Graz; Smart City Project, 2016 ^{34,35, 36}

As a kind of follow-up initiative to the ECO PROFIT project of the 1990, Graz has recently started an urban renewal project on the quarter level surrounding the railway station. By 2016, it is intended to almost reach the energetic self-sufficiency basically by use of photovoltaic's and geo thermal energy plus other 'smart' green technologies. A landmark will be a 40 meter high chimney with in-built wind generators.

Graz Science Tower with in-built chimney Source: Graz municipality. http://www.graz.at/cms/beitrag/10230840/1618648/	DNH_STRASSE_200dpi_Startseite.jpg Source: http://www.skyscrapercity.com/showthread.php?t=1504686

TOOL: Modular energy saving kits for house refurbishment

In mass housing schemes most units tend to have the same construction and typology and were built to low or medium standards. When it comes to urban renewal and revalorization the energy standards invariably have to be improved. By definition mass housing refers to a large number of units involved and therefore cost savings can be achieved through standardization and mass production of solutions which not only cater for insulation demand but also for the capture of natural energies.

Case Study: Denmark: Albertslund, 2011-12^{37,38, 39}

In the city of Albertslund, close to Copenhagen, a residential quarter of 2200 dwellings built between 1960 and 1980 needed to be upgraded to modern energy standards with the aim of achieving 73% energy savings. Apart from standard solutions involving passive wall and roof insulation, active solar gain shall be added by means of also prefabricated 'Solar

³⁴ <http://www.doiserbia.nb.rs/img/doi/0350-7599/2013/0350-75991304057C.pdf>, Page 68. Viewed 24/05/2015

³⁵ <http://www.stadtentwicklung.graz.at/cms/beitrag/10191841/4631044/> viewed 24/05/2015

³⁶ <http://www.smartcitygraz.at/> seen 22/07/2015

³⁷ <https://www.norden.org/sv/nordiska-ministerraadet/ministerraad/nordiska-ministerraadet-foer-naeringsliv-energi-och-regionalpolitik-mr-ner/nordiske-energikommuner/nominerade-kommuner/albertslund-kommunes-fact-sheet> viewed 25/05/2015

³⁸ <http://www.nordicenergymunicipality.org/> seen 02/06/2015

³⁹ http://www.klimabuendnis.org/fileadmin/inhalte/dokumente/MV2010/Niels_Carsten_Bluhme16042010_-_Climate_Plan_and_green_innovation.pdf viewed 25/05/2015

Prisms' to be placed on the roofs. These elements will contain solar water collectors, electro-voltaic cells, heat pumps, heat exchangers and roof lights.

<p>Typology of prefabricated houses to be refurbished <i>Source: Albertslund Municipality</i></p>	<p>The solar prism energy generation unit <i>Source: Albertslund municipality</i></p>

TOOL: District heating: Integrated heat-and-energy management

Individual house- or dwelling-based heating/cooling systems are less efficient than larger collective heat generation installations, also known as ‘co-generation’ of heat and power. The larger ones not only have lower investment cost per unit of energy but can also shift from one energy source (solar, natural or biogas, timber pellets etc.) to another dependent on cost and availability. They also have less consumption peaks and interruptions. Like in the case of autonomous energy supply described above they can make best use of waste heat invariably generated in the production process of electricity.

Case Study: Hamburg HafenCity district heating

In the huge renewal project of the former Hamburg harbour area; all buildings are connected to a district co-generation plant located within their reach, powered by solar-, geo-power and bio-gas in combination with heat storage facilities. This way, the CO₂ emission could be reduced from the typical 240g/kWh to only 175g/kWh.

3.1.4. Objective: Land recycling, brown field redevelopment

In a throw-away culture it seems normal to replace a torn product with a new one. This is fine where the resources are seemingly unlimited and affordable. Land, however, is a limited resource and is almost impossible to replace; or is even less capable of being moved from one place to another. This is a particularly painful experience in highly urbanized areas which all run out of land reserves. As it is the case with other resources, recycling is the second obvious solution to the problem after the first – acquisition of fresh land – has become almost impossible. The classical model of land recycling was dispossession of land reserves occupied by poor and powerless citizens, which is not only a humanitarian crime and even illegal in many places. A more practical answer would be to recycle unused and or abandoned land – like industrial plants or military camps.

TOOL: Concentration of smart solutions enterprises

Typical brown fields tend to be either defunct industrial sites or land formerly used by the military. A hazard can be soil pollution but the same may have developed a stable eco system with larger variety of species than elsewhere because no recent 'cultivation' history. Also now central location within the city may count on the positive side when considering renewal of brown fields offer attractive opportunities.

Case Study: Berlin EUREF-Campus, 2013⁴⁰⁴¹

The EUREF venture is one of the most remarkable and successful Brownfield renewal projects in Europe. It is located on the former City energy service field where the listed former gas tank with a height of 78 meters still remains and functions as a landmark or Icon of the new campus. The area covers 5,5 hectares and will eventually house more than 5000 workers in all kind of research and science companies engaging in energy, sustainability, environmental protection and mobility– some of them subsidiaries of big companies such as Cisco. Also a dependency of Berlin Technical University is present and runs three M.Sc. programs on site. The campus is planned as a living experiment for CO₂ free 'intelligent' or 'smart' cities. Already today in 2015, between 80 and 90 of all energy used on the campus are produced on-site and fed by sun, wind, biogas and geo-heat. Especially interesting is the Micro Smart Grid project which is connected to high capacity electrical battery and all energy users on the campus – including a fleet of e-cars.

⁴⁰ <http://www.businesslocationcenter.de/euref>, seen 16/07/2015;

⁴¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8i78cPev1BQ>, seen 16/07/2015;
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iIJ_a3Y8Khhg, seen 16/07/2015;

3.1.5. Objective; Land reclamation

Coastal cities often can enjoy the privileged location on the waterfront but this location also cuts the land reserve for expansion by half. Through land reclamation on shallow water extra and usually centrally located terrain can be created for urban development and provide resettlement reserves for historic and centrally located urban renewal programs. The term 'land reclamation' is sometimes also used for brown field development; redevelopment of harbour areas combines both interpretations.

TOOL: Creation of external overspill areas to accommodate greenery and/or housing as part of urban renewal programs

Land reclamation usually implies filling up the ground on shallow water with rocks or even sand – whatever is available and affordable. Obviously construction on this kind of land is more expensive than on solid land and usually requires pile foundation which can go rather deep.

Example: Venice San Giuliano Park, Italy^{42, 43}

San Giuliano reclamation area is a large urban park south of Maestre, overlooking the lagoon in front of Venice. Seven hundred hectares of greenery, the San Giuliano Park have been created in the first decade of this century and is the largest park Seven hundred hectares of greenery in front of Venice, the San Giuliano Park is the largest park in Europe and a recovered environment, cleaned up and used for the study of the lagoon's environment. Since there is a lack of green space in Venice, this area is to compensate for this deficit and is mainly used sports, recreational and cultural activities.

⁴² <http://www.veneziadavivere.com/en/city-guide/san-giuliano-park> visited 22/08/2015

⁴³ <http://www.veneziasi.it/content/view/?id=452&lang=en> visited 22/08/2015

<p>S, Guiliano Park Venice Source: <i>Comuna Venecia</i></p>	<p>S, Guiliano Park Venice Source: <i>Comuna Venecia</i> http://www.comune.venezia.it/flex/files/D.9d6fe3c886866fc2a7c2/2004_11_08_slide.pdf</p>

3.2.Strategy: Environmental Sustainability through Climate Change **Adaptation**⁴⁴

Contrary to Climate change mitigation, which attempts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, Adaptation Strategies also aim at reducing the vulnerability of cities against the negative effects of climate change.

3.2.1. Objective: Micro climate^{45, 46} / Heat island^{47, 48} reduction

'Urban areas generally have a lower humidity level than the surrounding countryside due to much absence of vegetation and the increased absorption of energy from the sun caused by dark asphalted or concrete surfaces. This also explains why inner city areas are often many degrees warmer than their surroundings. This phenomenon, known as the urban heat island effect, can have serious consequences for vulnerable people, such as those who are chronically ill or the elderly, particularly during heat waves. The moist air generated by natural vegetation helps to counter this phenomenon. Humidity levels could also be artificially increased using electricity to evaporate water, but this would cost significantly more than using natural vegetation (around €500,000 per hectare). Working with nature and using Green infrastructure in an urban environment, for example by incorporating biodiversity-rich parks, green spaces, green roofs and walls and fresh air corridors, is generally a much cheaper and more versatile option to help mitigate the urban heat island effect. It can also help to absorb CO₂ emissions, improve air quality, reduce rainfall runoff and increase energy efficiency'.⁴⁹

⁴⁴ <http://www.dw.com/en/climate-change-can-affect-all-of-us/a-17529180> seen 17/07/2015

⁴⁵ <http://www.gardening.cornell.edu/weather/microcli.html> seen 22/08/2015

⁴⁶ http://www.metoffice.gov.uk/media/pdf/n/9/Fact_sheet_No._14.pdf seen 22/08/2015

⁴⁷ <http://www.epa.gov/heatisland/about/index.htm> , <http://scied.ucar.edu/longcontent/urban-heat-islands> seen 17/07/2015

⁴⁸ <http://education.nationalgeographic.com/encyclopedia/urban-heat-island/> visited 22/08/2015

⁴⁹ Quotation from: http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/ecosystems/docs/green_infrastructure_broc.pdf, seen 17/07/2015

TOOL: Greening of streets, backyards and roofs⁵⁰

Urban greenery through evaporation can cool down ambient temperature. Secondly, by filtering the air fine dust particles can be retained, which are a major cause of smog, which caused by 'heavy' air building a sort of lid over the city and hinders natural thermal air circulation. Thirdly, psychologically the visual impact but also the movements of the leaves of plants give the impression of flowing air which the mind associates with a cooler environment.

Case study: Frankfurt green belt⁵¹

The GreenBelt is Frankfurt's "green lung" extending over 8,000 hectares cover around one-third of the surface area of the city and extending along some 70 km around it. It reveals the wide range of local landscapes and its orchard meadows, natural conservation areas, streams, farmland, parks, gardens, sports and leisure - areas are a microcosm of the different landscapes in the Rhine-Main Region.

Although having existed as a concept for long time before, only in 1991 it was decided to develop the area as a municipal green space and to place it under permanent protection. The medium-term goals are to give the Green Belt improved access and better connections to inner-city green spaces and open areas as well as to the recreation areas in the region. Already some green corridors have been driven into the inner city to facilitate air exchange and provide coherent corridors for the fauna.

<p><i>Frankfurt Green Belt plan, 2006</i></p> <p>Source: http://www.frankfurt-greencity.de/fileadmin/Redakteur_Dateien/kap09/09_kartegrueenanlagen2.jpg</p>	<p><i>Frankfurt green corridor plan to complement the existing greenbelt</i></p> <p>Source: https://www.eopinio.de/beteiligung/stadt/36/karte/14/seite/141</p>

⁵⁰ http://www.scp-knowledge.eu/sites/default/files/R%C3%B8m%C3%B8%202012%20Green%20roofs%20worldwide_0.pdf seen 21/07/2015

⁵¹ <http://www.frankfurt-greencity.de/en/environment-frankfurt/frankfurt-the-green-city/frankfurts-greenbelt/> seen 18/07/2015

3.2.2. Objective: Flood protection

Due to rising sea level or flooding of river basins many cities suffer from flooding every couple of years, whereby the frequency of those events tend to become closer due to climate change or deforestation (river basins).

TOOL: Sustainable Urban Drainage System (SUDS):

In the case of very heavy rains, which tend to occur more frequently now due to climate change, urban sewage system – especially in cities which don't operate a separate sewage and rain water drainage evacuation - are not capable of absorbing the masses of rain water and the resulting flooding causes not only material damage but also presents a health hazard after spilling of sewage into the floods. Comprehensive sewage systems aim at retaining rain water in open basins, for example football fields located slightly below street level, for a couple of hours. Other cities located on more permeable ground, now oblige owners of houses to provide for penetration of all rain water into the subsoil of the plot and do not tolerate rainwater to be led into the collective sewage system at all.

Case Study; Wolverhampton: Bilston Urban Village^{52,53}

Bilston Village is a good example for comprehensive Climate Change adaptation but stands out for the rain water retention aspect of it. The city is located in the West Midlands of the UK, close to Wolverhampton for which it serves as a residential overflow reserve for urban renewal. It occupies a 41 hectare site which is highly susceptible to flooding. In addition, 34 hectares consist of impermeable surfaces which make the land more vulnerable to surface water flooding. Several severe floods in the past led to high consideration of sustainable drainage features and attention to the contouring of the land. The specific Climate Change adaptation responses⁵⁴ to climate change include, among others, the following,

- Modification of pavement material designs to increase resistance to summer temperatures and by warmer winters. This required specific means to avoid cracking of concrete as a result of an increase in thermal expansion for concrete roads in summer.
- In order to deal with expected increase in rainfall intensity, additional flow paths for excess run off were installed and consideration was given to the levels of verges and surrounding topography.
- Drainage strategies were put into place to tackle possible weakening of the soil due to potential ground movements and change in soil moisture.
- Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS) were implemented to potentially reduce inflow to retention ponds and allow control flooding in other areas.

⁵² <http://www.bilstonurbanvillage.co.uk/> visited 22/08/2015

⁵³ <http://www.slideshare.net/chikoNcube/climate-change-adaptation-in-urban-regeneration-projects> , P. 47

⁵⁴ <http://www.dudley.gov.uk/easysiteweb/getresource.axd?assetid=13080&type=full&servicetype=a..> visited 22/08/2015

- The landscaping strategy implemented trees and plants selected for tolerance to anticipated changes in conditions. The landscape was also utilised in close relation to its built element during the construction phase.
- Future increase in demand for water supply was considered in the water features.

Figure 2: showing proposed comprehensive drainage strategy (Source: Wolverhampton City Council, 2010)

TOOL: Water proof ground floors and pedestrian access above street level.

Dykes around the city were a traditional remedy against flood damage, but they are not always feasible or would separate the city from the water front. Steel shutters are a feasible alternative and additionally provide physical protection against break-ins and damage in connection with violent mass manifestations.

Case Study: Hamburg HafenCity redevelopment^{55, 56}

The new HafenCity brown field mixed use redevelopment covers the former harbour site and extends the downtown area by about 50% connecting it to the river Elbe. Occasional high tides of the North Sea also reach Hamburg and then drown parts part of the city. For this eventuality the ground floor openings of the new adjacent buildings can be shut and protected by steel shutters. Additionally, car traffic and pedestrian movement have been separated by adding a pedestrian circulation system above street level

Historical Hamburg Harbour - recently added to the acknowledged the World Heritage List by UNESCO. Note the high basement for flood protection,
Foto: Kosta Mathéy

A recently redeveloped part of Hamburg Hafen City, introducing a wide pedestrian promenade with coffee shops on the ground that can be closed by waterproof doors and shutters in case of high floods.
Foto: Kosta Mathéy

⁵⁵ <http://www.hamburg.de/stadtplanung/projekte/hafencity/> visited 27/05/2015

⁵⁶ <http://www.hafencity.com/de/konzepte/stadt-des-21-jahrhunderts.html> visited 27/05/2015

TOOL: Floating homes.

'Special planning for floating apartments is one way to adapt to the effects of rising sea levels and increasing rainfall due to climate change. According to experts from the Dutch government's Delta Commission, the sea level will rise in the country by 1.3 meters (4.3 feet) in the next century, and up to 4 meters (13 feet) over the next 200 years. One-third of the Netherlands is situated either at sea level, or below it'.⁵⁷

'There are two types of floating homes, permanently floating homes and homes that float only when flood waters swell, but sit on the ground during the dry season. Requiring floatability for new construction within floodplains, and considering same for threatened shore lines, is one way to plan for the future. Although floating homes near the coast need protected waters, like wave attenuation through wave walls and dykes (as used in Europe) they represent a future urbanization possibility'.⁵⁸

Case Study: Amsterdam, IJburg and Steigereiland floating housing. 2009^{59,60,61,62}

The idea for Amsterdam's floating city was born during a land shortage. However, Amsterdam carries a long tradition of houseboat living—about 2,300 converted barges float along the capital's canals—and reimagine it as a contemporary community.

Whilst planning IJburg dates from 2009 onwards, the urban expansion project to the east of Amsterdam, Steigereiland ('jetty island') was designated as experimental area. IJburg lies on man-made islands in the IJmeer, without the ring-dike that is common in conventional reclamation practices. At Steigereiland, the base of the building is filled with cement and heavy-duty foam. Rings attached to sunken posts make sure the house stays up. They also

⁵⁷ <http://www.dw.com/en/floating-houses-to-fight-climate-change-in-holland/a-17532376> seen 17/07/2015

⁵⁸ <http://www.inspirationgreen.com/floating-homes.html>, seen 17/07/2015

⁵⁹ <http://time.com/2926425/the-floating-homes/> viewed 04/06/2015

⁶⁰ <http://www.e-architect.co.uk/amsterdam/floating-house-ijburg> viewed 04/06/2015

⁶¹ <http://www.a-realestate.it/opencms/export/sites/default/allegati/AmsterdamFloating.pdf> viewed 04/06/2015

⁶² <http://www.dac.dk/en/dac-cities/sustainable-cities/all-cases/master-plan/ijburg-city-of-islands/> viewed 04/06/2015

allow the structure to move up and down, depending on water level. As a result, the water is present all around, giving the district its unique and distinct character as city archipelago.

3.2.3. Objective: Drought precaution

Climate change not only brings too much water to certain regions, but takes it away from others which were used to receive sufficient quantities in the past. We know from history that complete cities were abandoned when the water supply ceased. Given size of modern cities, and the vanishing of land reserves on habitable land, the solution of just moving a city is not feasible any more.

TOOL: Rainwater harvesting and Green Roofs

Ancient cities in dry regions were used to collect rain water and store it in cisterns for the months with little rainfall. Of course, it is not very easy to store the water needs for an entire season in a cistern, but since most of the collected water is not meant for drinking anyway but mostly for watering gardens, storage can also happen in the subsoil and pumped from there again.

Type of green roofs	Extensive	Semi-intensive	Intensive
Use	Environmental landscape	Gardens/ environmental landscape	Gardens/ parks
Type of vegetation	Mosses, herbs, grass	Grass, herbs, shrubs	Lawn, perennial plants, shrubs, trees
Watering	None	Periodically	Regularly
Depth of substrate	60-200 mm	120-250 mm	150-400 mm
Weight	60-150 kg/m	120-200 kg/m	180-500 kg/m
Costs	Low	Middle	High
The choice of plants, thickness, weight, and maintenance are connected.			
<i>Different types of Green Roofs</i>			
Source: Copenhagen Adaptation and resilient infrastructure ^{63, 64}			

⁶³ <http://designtoimprovelife.dk/danish-capital-adapts-succesfully-to-changing-climate/> seen 02/06/2015

⁶⁴ <https://vimeo.com/69160394/> seen 02/06/2015

Case study; Copenhagen Green Roofs Program, 2010^{65,66,67}

Already in 2008 the City of Copenhagen began exploring alternative ways to handle rainwater in the city. In 2009, Denmark was in charge of the UN Climate Change Conference COP15 which defined the framework for the strategies that could be implemented for meeting the challenges of climate change. During that period, the focus on green roofs intensified setting a goal for urban design with green roofs in the Climate Plan of the City of Copenhagen. Since then Green Roofs have become integrated in different guidelines such as the Guidelines for Sustainability in Constructions and Civil works, which mandates green roofs for all the Municipalities buildings. Green roofs are also a part of the city's Strategy for Biodiversity. Already from 2010 onwards, green roofs are mandated in most new local plans. A calculation based on approved new local plans mandating green roofs gives a total of 200.000 m² of green roofs to be installed.

In Europe, green roofs can absorb between 50% and 80 % of the annual rainfall. Some of the water evaporates and cools the air in that way. Rainwater from the roof will be collected and utilised on the property for watering, recreational purposes or similar, while rainwater from certain areas is redirected to flush the sewage system given that it is badly polluted.

Green roofs also support biodiversity. They lead to larger quantities of rainwater being absorbed in a sustainable way and can curb the rise in temperature at the same time. Green roofs are therefore part of the City of Copenhagen's Climate Plan and Climate Adaptation Plan. Green roofs also create habitats for animals and plants and in this way support biodiversity. For these reasons, they have become integrated in the City of Copenhagen's Strategy for Biodiversity.

⁶⁵ http://www.klimatilpasning.dk/media/631048/green_roofs_copenhagen.pdf seen 21/07/2015

⁶⁶ <http://video.denmark.dk/video/2316953/green-rooftops> seen

⁶⁷ www.pri.org/stories/2014-12-05/its-not-just-bikes-green-rooftops-make-copenhagen-greenest-green-cities , viewed 21/07/2015

3.2.4. Objective: Integrated flood prevention and erosion control

The previous example which focuses on the improvement of the micro climate where water resource conservation will improve the comfort levels in cities but is not enough to prevent and handle serious disaster scenarios. This requires a combination of many different measures together with a tested emergency plan. An example of such integrated and cooperative strategy could exist of different elements such as:

- a) Roadways redesigned for water management
- b) shift away from 'grey' towards 'blue and green' infrastructure
- c) Responsibility of private property owners

TOOL: Integrated disaster prevention planning

Where rainwater harvesting or retention or infiltration technologies are applied individually, disaster prevention requires a concerted intervention plan for the worst-case scenario. This means that efforts to reduce the impact of climate change are not enough but a possibly necessary rescue plan must be elaborated in parallel.

Case Study: Copenhagen Climate Adaptation Plan 2011⁶⁸

Copenhagen is taking the lead in combining green roofs, rainwater drainage and flood control with other key plans for green, sustainable, social and economic development. The principle strategies can be summarized in three points:

- Minimizing potential damage arising from climate change.
- Warning and response systems to deal with abnormal conditions.
- Preventive infrastructure to cope with damage, loss and traffic disruption

For example: In heavy rains the green roof delays the water on its way to the sewers and thus reduces the hazard of flooding at the peak of a rainfall. For this reason, green roofs form part of the Climate Plan and the Climate Adaptation Plan of the City of Copenhagen.

The Copenhagen Climate Adaptation Plan recognises the need to combine and reinforce the 'green' and 'blue' infrastructure in order to manage and retain storm water flows. This leads to more surface conveyance and retention of water in the future, and less reliance on sub-surface systems. Challenges remain in respect to governance, management and financing issues in terms of Public-Private Partnership.

- Roadway design plays an important role because roads are the principal corridors through which the population at risk can be evacuated and over which assistance can be brought in.
- Utility companies are publicly-owned but operate as corporations in Denmark and investments are normally captured through

⁶⁸ <http://designtoimprovelife.dk/danish-capital-adapts-succesfully-to-changing-climate/>

charges paid by ratepayers. Planning regulations already favour a shift away from 'grey' towards 'blue and green' infrastructure, but as a new tool require constant monitoring and adjustment.

- Lastly, private property owners need to accept the responsibility for providing adequate installations on their individual plot, such as backflow valves and storm water resilient roof or ground vegetation.

Taken together, the Climate Adaptation Plan sets the framework for Danish designers, architects and engineers cooperating in designing solutions for a climate resilient metropolis of the 21st century. The Danish capital Copenhagen received INDEX: Award 2013 for the city's climate adaptation plan, a plan that provides a unique and robust framework for a massive influx of sustainable design solutions in the future.

<p>Flooding of the streets of Copenhagen after an extraordinary storm</p> <p><i>Source:</i> http://syncrostudio.com/copenhagen-planning-for-adaptation-to-changing-climate/</p>	<p>Illustration of sustainable Water management</p> <p><i>Source:</i> http://designtoimprovelife.dk/danish-capital-adapts-succesfully-to-changing-climate/</p>

3.3. Strategy: Environmental sustainability

Climate change is only one factor which has an influence on the environment and on the material and on the spiritual base of our well-being. Ecological diversity and air quality also impact on mankind future living chances and conditions. When a food chain is broken, the consequences can be much bigger than removing a single link in the chain. If we use up certain mineral resources they will be missing for our grand-children.

3.3.1. Objective: Combating resource depletion

Measured by the relatively short period that mankind has conquered our planet, the speed in which we use up the earth's 'non-renewable' resources is irresponsible, nor economically sensitive. Most of resource depletion is linked to the urban economy and development. This is why stopping this process, in general, has to begin in the cities first.

TOOL: Municipally led waste and resource management

Priorities in resource preservation go from avoidance to recycling and only in the last consequence to safe disposal. In fact, the most active municipalities in fighting Climate Change include some waste directed modules in their strategy.

<p>Malmö Priority Urban Development Areas Source: http://www.fomento.gob.es/NR/rdonlyres/9D6A5DD0-D460-4728-9882-71E4E5EDD3EF/95899/5.pdf</p>	<p>Malmö waste separation and recollection Photo: shutterstock_206454547_ah_70038</p>

Case Study: Malmö Environmental Programme 2009 – 2020^{69, 70}

Malmö is working towards becoming a leading Eco City and plans to achieve 100% use of renewable energy by 2010. Apart from other remarkable the city-wide initiatives, some more neglected areas have been selected for area-based urban renewal initiatives, like one of the city's Priority Urban Development areas called Ekostaden Augustenborg (dating from 1948) with some 3000 inhabitants and a number of industries. The applied measures combine energy saving campaigns, social and infrastructure assistance. The garbage issue was only a minor component but nevertheless was able to achieve a 70% reduction in waste that had to be removed from the area. In another Priority development Area, Bo1-City of Tomorrow, organic waste and municipal waste water is used for the production of Biogas which satisfies 3% of all municipal heat supply.

⁶⁹ http://www.movium.slu.se/sites/default/files/course/9904/files/documentation/peter_om_nr_2.pdf viewed 22/05/2015

⁷⁰ <http://www.fomento.gob.es/NR/rdonlyres/9D6A5DD0-D460-4728-9882-71E4E5EDD3EF/95899/5.pdf> viewed 27/05/2015

Energy production from bio waste in Malmö

Source; <http://www.fomento.gob.es/NR/rdonlyres/9D6A5DD0-D460-4728-9882-71E4E5EDD3EF/95899/5.pdf>

3.3.2. Objective: Preserving Biodiversity

Every day species' extinctions are ascending up to 1,000 times or more of the natural rate.⁷¹ 18,788 species out of 52,017 so far assessed are threatened with extinction – and most of them directly or indirectly due to anthropogenic disturbance in the world ecological balance.⁷² Paradoxically, sometimes there still is a larger variety of species inside cities than in the countryside where monoculture and heavy use of pesticides still dominate. But even so, urbanization is not a safeguard against biodiversity loss, since farm products are mostly consumed in cities and pesticides are produced there too. Nevertheless, consciousness building as well as practical support to conservation can start from the cities.

TOOL: Community gardens and diversity of species

The promotion of school and community gardens follows an education effort in the first place, community building in the second and food production last. Usually there is some social staff taking care of attendance, and collective activities stand in the centre.

⁷¹ https://www.iucn.org/iyb/about/biodiversity_crisis/ seen 7/22/2015

⁷² <http://www.who.int/globalchange/ecosystems/biodiversity/en/> seen 7/22/2015

Case Study: Brussels: L'îlot Fontainas

As part of the city-wide quarter renewal program several 'lighthouse projects' have been realized right at the beginning of the initiative, one of which is the settlement *Jardin des Fleurs* at *Ilot Fontainois*. It stands for sustainable urbanization but goes a step further and foresees a public park specifically designed to preserve local species of flora and fauna. Locally indigenous trees and other plants are being planted with the idea that they will also attract the native fauna.

<p><i>Participatory Planning at Ilot Fontainas</i> http://architecte.b612associates.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/DSC07386_resultat.jpg</p>	<p>Model of Ilot Fontainas Source: http://architecte.b612associates.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/1301_Maquette_FON11_featured.jpg</p>

TOOL: Urban Forestry ⁷³.

Forests usually provoke the association with wilderness and incompatible with urban civilisation. Nevertheless, for many urbanites, hiking through the forest ranks among the most exciting Sunday afternoon occupations. For some 20 years there already exists an initiative to complement the urban gardening movement by advocating the alternative of urban forestry – even some M.Sc. programs on the topic have opened recently in European Universities. It must be remembered though that urban forest already existed centuries ago when they were attached to Baroque Palaces (Versailles in France, Tiergarten in Berlin Germany) and functioned as hunting grounds for the nobles while not being open to the public. Only with the French revolution this exclusiveness changed: the Paris Bois de Boulogne was arranged for public use of citizens and in Northern Europe (Skandinavia, Netherlands, Britain) they used to be commons.

⁷³ <http://scenariojournal.com/article/beyond-planting/> seen 7/23/2015

Case Study: Leipzig, Urban Forestry^{74,75,76}

After German reunification, the former socialist part of the country was quickly depopulated because of the better income opportunities in the West. The second biggest Eastern German city, Leipzig, lost more than a third of its former population and many houses fell into decay and had to be demolished. A new land use was to be found for the empty sites and for that reason the interest for urban forestry started there in the 1990s. One argumentation in favour of urban forestry were significantly less maintenance costs compared to conventional urban green areas. The proposal was to generally introduce urban forestry as a new and additional the land use category in Germany. Initially three urban plots were to be prepared for urban forestry and the feedback from the users collected and evaluated.

⁷⁴ http://www.mil.brandenburg.de/media_fast/4055/Freiraeume_Dokumentation_Teil2_20110606.pdf viewed 27/05/2015

⁷⁵ http://www.ufz.de/export/data/424/34785_ConferenceGuide_EFUF_2012_web.pdf, page 24 viewed 27/05/2015

⁷⁶ <http://www.la.rwth-aachen.de/Forschung/PDF/wald%20als%20qualitaet.pdf>. viewed 7/24/2015

Hoher Wald Mehrschichtig dicht	Hoher Wald Mehrschichtig licht	Hoher Wald Einschichtig dicht	Hoher Wald Einschichtig licht	Niedriger Bestand mit einzelnen Bäumen	Niedriger Bestand aus Gebüsch und Niederwald arten
Stadt Leipzig	„Urbaner Wald“	Freiräume in der schrumpfenden Stadt		Potsdam	7. April 2011
Leipzig: selected wood typologies suitable for urban forestry Source: http://www.mil.brandenburg.de .					

Case Study; Forest City Halle Silberhöhe^{77,78,79}

Halle is an industrial city in Eastern Germany. For the industry workers a huge mass housing district was built for some 40,000 inhabitants. After reunification the local industries closed down and the population declined to less than half. Part of the depopulated housing blocks were pulled down and the recovered space was transformed into a forest with many different kind of trees, following the new concept of a ‘forest city’. In fact, for each remaining resident two new trees were planted.

Partial demolition of mass housing in Halle Silberhöhe after reunification Source: https://www.google.com/search?newwindow=1&biw=1024&bih=698&site=imghp&tbn=isch&sa=1&q=waldstadt+silberh%C3%B6he+abriss&oq=waldstadt+silberh%C3%B6he+abriss&gs_l=img.3...689242.690852.0.691978.7.7.0.0.0.0.263.900.3j3j1.7.0...0...1c.1.64.img..7.0.0.VEhI0BTx7Dw#imgrc=DP9L8_tZY_PepM%3A	Vision of future Forest City Siberhöhe Source: http://cad.burg-halle.de/typo3temp/pics/90a9f40be3.jpg

⁷⁷ <http://www.werkstatt-stadt.de/de/projekte/138/>. viewed 7/24/2015

⁷⁸ <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Halle-Silberh%C3%B6he> viewed 7/24/2015

⁷⁹ <http://www.diercke.de/content/halle-silberh%C3%B6he-umbau-zur-waldstadt-978-3-14-100700-8-39-4-0> viewed 7/24/2015

3.3.3. Objective: Healthy cities – healthy living

Flora and fauna are not the only endangered species, but also mankind. Back in the 1970s and 1980s there was a growing criticism against living in buildings which had been conceived as a machine by its architects, and some (mostly underground) architects in Berkeley (US) and Germany promoted Biological Building instead. They avoided cancerogenic and other dangerous chemical substances as components in building materials, concentrations of electromagnetic fields. Most buildings were either individual houses or settlements at the fringe of the city, but some coherent urban renewal programs also adopted biological building principles, like in Germany the International Building Exhibition (IBA) in its urban renewal site.⁸⁰ The WHO (World Health Organization) also took up the issue and discussed it in the context of the Healthy Home.⁸¹

More recent projects – mostly in overspill areas and not in the city centres, combine certain ecological building principles with other sustainable settlement features, like car sharing arrangements or energy self-sufficiency. Famous examples include the French Quarter in German Tübingen⁸² or Freiburg-Vauban.⁸³

<p><i>Ecological Settlement in Darmstadt-Kranichstein, Germany.</i> Source: Kosta Mathéy</p>	<p><i>Ecological settlement Vauban in Freiburg, Germany</i> Source: https://www.parismatch.com/Actu/Societe/Fribourg-en-Brisgau-le-paradis-a-l-allemande-1642009</p>

TOOL: Provision of space for urban agriculture

Over the last 30 years there has been a revival of urban farming practices – though less for the pure material need to supplement personal food supply (as it was in the post war period of WWI and II), but rather in the intention to improve

⁸⁰ <http://f-iba.de/>, https://www.google.de/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=5&ved=0CEoQFjAEahUKEwi2_7f0hPDGAhWIOxQKHZaU-AEq&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.stadtentwicklung.berlin.de%2Fstaedtebau%2Fbaukultur%2Fiba%2Fdownload%2Flearning_from_IBA.pdf&ei=4zqwVfaBD4j3UJapgsAE&usq=AFQjCNFVeyxv9SDICNg_ygFvIvwdqaWOTA&sig2=TU1XLYp4pRV6OSLmN8DuAw

⁸¹ http://www.who.int/healthy_settings/types/homes/en/, <http://www.who.int/hia/housing/en/>,

⁸² <http://www.geolinde.musin.de/stadt/stadt/franzviertel/> seen 7/23/2015

⁸³ <http://www.freiburg.de/pb/,Lde/208732.html> seen 7/23/2015

living standards through close contact to nature and possibly also consuming healthier food.

Case Study: Brussels: Les potagers de Canal-Midi⁸⁴

As part of the city wide quarter renewal program several 'lighthouse projects' have been realized right at the beginning of the initiative, one of which is the 'sustainable quarter' Canal Midi at Anderlecht which could not be perceived without the availability of sustainable food supply and nutrition. Therefore an area of 3500 m² was converted into productive gardens for the residents of large housing estates, and an organic food restaurant was also added to stimulate residents to reflect their eating habits.

Les potagers de Canal-Midi Source: http://vertdiris.net/le-potager/	Les potagers de Canal-Midi Source: http://vertdiris.net/le-potager/

Case Study: Organic food promotion in Copenhagen, Denmark

City of Copenhagen set an initial goal of procuring at least 75 percent organic food in 2012. This target was met and it now aims to procure 90 percent organic food by 2015. This organic purchasing objective is seen as an important source of creating food literacy among children and young people, and for promoting healthier eating amongst the population in general. Increasing the demand for organic food is also viewed as a tool in maintaining groundwater quality in areas adjoining Copenhagen, as the organic goal is coupled with initiatives to source locally.

⁸⁴ <http://vertdiris.net/contrat-de-quartier-durable-canal-midi/> seen 7/23/2015

Case Study: 'Sargfabrik' Urban Renewal Projects in Vienna, Austria⁸⁵

Sargfabrik is a residential complex for 120 people, located on a former coffin manufacture built in 1895. It is one of the pioneer projects in creating apartments on former factory sites. In Sargfabrik environmental aspects are strongly taken into account. Applied concepts are: optimized energy consumption (energy-saving technology, good insulation), composting, solar water heating, heating for the pool is secured by PV panels, large windows allow maximum use of sunlight. Parking spaces are reduced to minimum.

In the inner courtyard and a rooftop garden fruits and vegetables are grown by residents. Benefits of a green roof are reductions in energy consumption and carbon emission, reduced risk of flooding (due to absorption by the substrate and plants), improved local climate, pleasant and healthy environment, reduced traffic for transportation of goods, reduction in the transportation of the food (since part of food grown directly on the site), use of local compost, high degree of self-sufficiency, more control over the products, maintenance of biodiversity and the natural environment, as well as reduction of visual pollution caused by the light and provision of recreational activities on the location. An integrated irrigation system and rainwater collection were not provided since that technology was not available at the time of the construction.

Sargfabrik in Vienna with urban gardening on roof top and inner courtyards. Foto: [Vienez](#). Source: <http://www.shareable.net/blog/public-housing-works-lessons-from-vienna-and-singapore>

Sargfabrik settlement by bkk-2 Architektur. Photo: Müry Salzmann Verlag

3.3.4. Objective: Clean and fair building materials

Ecological construction defines certain standards, such as the absence of poisonous ingredients and complying with basic workers rights including healthy working conditions. With accelerating globalization it becomes more

⁸⁵ <http://www.doiserbia.nb.rs/img/doi/0350-7599/2013/0350-75991304057C.pdf>, Page 63. Viewed 24/05/2015

difficult to assure the compliance with the standards as a large number of products or their components are imported from far away countries with little possibilities to enforce fair standards.

TOOL: Green Public Procurement policy

Urban infrastructure and public buildings are mostly paid by the exchequer and represent a large proportion of the construction sector. Since these works normally must be tendered, this is the opportunity to enforce the desired ecological standards, if intended, by the politicians

Case study: Green public tendering in Frankfurt/Germany⁸⁶

Frankfurt, the Europe Clean Capital finalist of 2012, has published a Green City Agenda including energy saving guidelines and regulations to include ecological criteria in the tendering of Municipal Buildings. Binding environmental procurement rules have been adopted e.g. a ban of tropical wood and PVC, use of recycled paper etc. Local utilities have adopted guidelines following ISO 14001 or similar and are regularly audited.

3.3.5. Objective: Air pollution control

Air pollution may have many causes, including industries, road traffic, smog and sand storms (still very rarely in Europe) and others. Specific tools must be chosen carefully

TOOLS against pollution generated by local industries

Typical remedies are subsidies or loans to the industries to modernize their production process or relocation:

Case study: the ECOPROFIT Program in Graz. (also mentioned above)

The city of Graz with about 250.000 inhabitants is situated in basin topography. And Graz is an important industrial area. The combination of these two reasons associated with inversion weather caused great troubles with smog especially in winter. In 1989 the city of Graz decided, that it was time for a change. The **target** was the reduction of emissions and impacts on the environment. The environmental department worked together with the Technical University of Graz to find possibilities to guarantee ecological success for the region as well as economic success for the companies to get them involved.

The public - private partnership programme ECOPROFIT was born. The combination of corporate training of the companies by consultants and authorities as well as consultancy in the compa-

86

https://www.google.co.uk/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=2&ved=0CDMQFjABahUKEwiy89f9i_LGAhWG2ywKHeOrCvc&url=http%3A%2F%2Fec.europa.eu%2Fenvironment%2Furopeangreencapital%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2011%2F04%2FMDR0763Rp00011a-Synopsis-Technical-Assessment-Report.pdf&ei=vU6xVfKgCoa3swHj16q4Dw&usg=AFQjCNEnwf0-25GJoTqKifCuiBMNS21Pqw&bvm=bv.98476267,d.bGg&cad=rja

nies succeeded. These successes increased by cooperation and communication among the companies

ECOPROFIT substantially contributed to the attainment of the target in Graz, to stop the smog. That has been yielded in the winter 1995/96. Since then in Graz there has not seen any smog any more.

<p><i>Air pollution in Graz, Austria,</i></p> <p><i>Source:</i> http://kurier.at/lebensart/motor/feinstaub-das-winterproblem/732.842</p>	<p><i>Graz on a clear day</i></p> <p><i>Source:</i> http://static.habsburger.net/files/styles/large/public/originale/graz_altstadt_dom_und_mausoleum_ferdinands_ii_1614-1638_original.jpg</p>

TOOLS against pollution caused by heavy traffic⁸⁷

The best remedy against smog is stopping through traffic all together, like the car free zones like the CBDs of Milan, Florence or Lisbon. The second best option would be to reduce the speed of traffic, i.e. by uneven road surface (bumpers), non-synchronised traffic lights, mixed use of road space by cars and pedestrians.⁸⁸ Especially bad are exhaust fumes from gas oil cars without filters.

<p><i>Car free zone in the historic centre of Lisbon</i></p> <p><i>Photo: Kosta Mathy</i></p>	<p><i>Rome, Italy. Traffic calming near railway station</i></p> <p><i>Foto: Kosta Mathy</i></p>

⁸⁷ <http://www.frankfurt-greencity.de/en/environment-frankfurt/the-air-in-frankfurt/> seen 7/24/2015

⁸⁸ <https://www.google.co.uk/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=5&ved=0CDcQFjAEahUKEwiW26iWoPLGAhWEFCwKHcArCKg&url=http%3A%2F%2Flibrary.ite.org%2Fpub%2F277e2be-2354-d714-519b-fdd0b98f0d7d&ei=6WOxVdbCIISpsAHA16DACg&usq=AFQjCNHOL8ja2RHil4VORdUW3HrJBEkNJQ&cad=rja>

Case Study: Bologna, Italy⁸⁹

Motor vehicle traffic in many Italian cities has become unbearable for residents and visitors alike in the last decade. The impact of traffic accidents, congestion and extremely destructive air pollution has prompted a number of cities to close off large downtown areas to all but essential traffic---i.e. non commuters (tourists) and those with a final destination in the downtown such as residents and merchants. The first and also most successful of the Italian cities to introduce this kind of area-wide traffic restraint was Bologna – initially only restricting individual traffic in the historical centre. Under a slogan of "A City for Living" the authorities have recently tightened again access to streets in the historic central district while improving bus, trolley, and metro services. In the restricted area, "Zona Traffico Limitato"(ZTL) in the centre of the city access is authorized only to local inhabitants or to individuals destined for a hotel in the restricted zone. The ZTL-zone is controlled by video cameras.

TOOLS against smog:

Smog is partly an effect of air pollution and not a cause. Therefore the last two tools will also remove smog. Complementary to that air circulation through the city can be improved (where topography allows) through cutting green corridors through the city.

⁸⁹ US dept of transportation, Publication No. FHWA-PD-93-028.1994. Case study 19, page 23.
https://www.google.co.uk/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=2&ved=0CCQQFjABahUKEwiW26iWoPLGAhWEF-CwKHcArCKg&url=http%3A%2F%2Fsafety.fhwa.dot.gov%2Fped_bike%2Fdocs%2Fcase19.pdf&ei=6WOxVdbCIIspSAHA16DACg&usq=AFQjCNGxII0eQM7GMVew2AFojxqvifeLSQ&cad=rja

3.3.6. Objective: Noise pollution control

Noise pollution can cause disruption, interference and irritation and can in some cases lead to the development of stress or loss of sleep. So maintaining the comfort and well-being of people in their own homes is important – not just to protect human rights but also to help sustain a happy, healthy and productive society.⁹⁰

TOOLS: Traffic calming, road closures

If quiet zones are included in the master plan, then traffic planners can direct traffic to arterial roads and ensure that traffic stays outside the residential neighbourhood. Alternatively they can regulate traffic speeds to reduce noise levels during specific hours of the day or at night. The European Noise Directive⁹¹ regulates the assessment and management of environmental noise. Another EU document⁹² states, "First conservative and partial estimates show that at least 1.600.000 Disability Adjusted Life Years are lost every year in the EU, mostly due to road traffic (noise)." The directive requires all cities and agglomerations of more than 100,000 inhabitants to assess the noise exposure of people in their residence. Buses, city utility vehicles and garbage trucks can be noisy, and it is expensive to replace them with quieter models.

To set a policy in place, the planning department of a community needs to present a cost/benefit analysis to enforce the improvements. A noise analysis and prognosis can pinpoint which school, hospital and neighbourhood is improved by what margin for a variety of noise solutions.⁹³

Case study: City of Odense (Denmark) Traffic calming 2009^{94,95,96}

Odense is the 3rd biggest city in Denmark, and used to be the traffic nerve centre of Denmark. The attempt to keep cars out of the city centre represents a break from 50 years of urban planning. The main street through the city centre, previously used by 35,000 cars per day, was closed for motorized traffic. The remainder of Odense's central area was divided into four zones, and motorists may not cross directly between one to the next zone. Instead a new Parking route was established in surrounding streets and motorists are being guided to the nearest free parking lot. A speed limit is enforced on the Parking Route to reduce noise and air pollution. This measure counted on inducing a traffic modal split and aimed 60% more bike rides and 60% fewer traffic deaths by 2025, an increase of public transport by 200%, to have 75% less people burdened by harmful pollution and 90% less burdened by traffic noise.

⁹⁰ <http://noisenuisance.org/> viewed 24/07/2015

⁹¹ http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1435827004963&uri=OJ:JOL_2015_168_R_0001 viewed 24/07/2015

⁹² <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/noise/home.htm>, viewed 24/07/2015

⁹³ http://www.soundplan.com/noise-control.htm?gclid=ClnetJCv8sYCFRLMtAodPb0A_g viewed 7/24/2015

⁹⁴ <http://www.dac.dk/en/dac-cities/sustainable-cities/all-cases/transport/odense-masterplan-for-sustainable-mobility/>, seen 7/24/2015

⁹⁵ <http://www.danishnet.com/travel-denmark/odense-denmark/> seen 24/07/2015

⁹⁶ <http://www.eltis.org/discover/case-studies/improving-accessibility-senior-friendly-walking-routes-odense-denmark> seen 7/24/2015

Odense city transformed main street

Source;

http://www.dac.dk/media/32568/Odense_juulfrost_TBT_midterfoto_besk%C3%A55ret.jpg

Case study: Noise Action Plan in Frankfurt, Germany 2010⁹⁷

Frankfurt is assumed to be Germany's central traffic hub, therefore noise protection is a key topic in the municipal strategies with the public being involved in the noise abatement plan.⁹⁸ The Frankfurt Noise action plan of 2010 concerns mostly mobility, with the goals established at "reducing noise pollution so as to maintain and improve the city's residential quality". Envisaged measures include low noise road surfaces, upgrading of rail routes, increasing the share of bicycles, and traffic management including an impressive catalogue of aircraft procedures for air traffic noise abatement.

Noise emission plan and possible noise abatement measures in Frankfurt

Source: <http://www.frankfurt-greencity.de>

3.4. Strategy: Economic Sustainability

⁹⁷ <http://www.frankfurt-greencity.de/en/environment-frankfurt/noise-in-frankfurt/>, viewed 7/24/2015

⁹⁸ <http://www.frankfurt-greencity.de/en/environment-frankfurt/noise-in-frankfurt/reducing-noise-pollution/noise-abatement-planning/>, seen 7/24/2015

If urban renewal projects fail, it is mostly because of economic reasons. This may be during the actual project implementation period, or in the long run because the incomes by the resident population are insufficient to keep up with the improved standards and induce gentrification or renewed decay for lack of maintenance (maintenance costs are not covered). This is not the fault of the target group but the lack long term economic foresight on behalf of the planners. This is not really a surprise since urban planners never learned about economics nor have any powers to interfere in this field. There are, however, also some positive experiences in economically sustainable urban renewal which will be discussed in the following section.

3.4.1. Objective: Public-private partnerships

For quite an extended period already, disposable state income tends to decrease while at the same time neoliberal local authorities are less prepared to finance public services and investments. It is also true that private investors are more flexible and less bureaucratic in project administration, at the cost of lacking social accountability and the need to be able to withhold a compatible profit margin. A possible third player in municipal governance is the social sector who represents the resident population. Well managed cooperation of the three sectors: state, private and social sectors, is known as participatory governance,^{99, 100, 101} where part of the costs can be covered by community itself.

Tool: Soft Renewal:

Urban renewal is expensive; but it also creates economic values which accrue to the house owner's assets. Soft renewal means animating landlords to invest without using the instrument of expropriation.

Case Study: Vienna ecological block renewal program, 1996-2001^{102,103}

The Project "Ecological Block Renewal" is a key project of the Viennese URBAN program and is winner of the *UN Habitat best Practice* award. Developed by the Vienna Land Procurement and Urban Renewal Fund (WBSF), this project aims at connecting the objectives of soft urban renewal with ecological measures and activities for local business enterprises.

Technically speaking the approach is the so-called "inner urban development" as a more economical alternative compared to urban expansion with much higher infrastructure costs. In this particular case, some of blocks within the program had been original-

⁹⁹ <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1467-7660.2009.01586.x/abstract> visited 23/08/2015

¹⁰⁰

https://books.google.de/books?id=nTQAAgAAQBAJ&dq=richard+stren,+participatory+governance&lr=&source=gbs_navlinks_s visited 23/08/2015

¹⁰¹ <file:///C:/Users/Kosta/Downloads/cusp-110108-participatory-gov.pdf> visited 23/08/2015

¹⁰² http://mirror.unhabitat.org/bp/bp.list.details.aspx?bp_id=2402 accessed 22/05/2015

<https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=images&cd=&ved=0CAUQjhxqFQoTCKvBxs7e4cYCFVer2wodARsDsQ&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.wohnbauforschung.at%2Findex.php%3Finc%3Ddownload%26id%3D5552&ei=rruoVaayN9HW7AaBtoylCw&psig=AFQjCNH48hUfBXsG6AaliaSBYqRK4cdaGg&st=1437207782757146> accessed 17/07/2015

¹⁰³ http://mirror.unhabitat.org/bp/bp.list.details.aspx?bp_id=2402 accessed 22/05/2015

ly constructed around the turn of the century (1900) and are situated along the western Guertel road in a very densely built up quarter. The technical equipment of most dwellings in these areas is still very poor. There is a significant lack of green spaces and the unemployment rate is higher than the Viennese average.

As part of the project, house based renewal opportunities are being discussed with the individual owners and supported projects may receive a maximum 30 % financial contribution for all expenses from the EU URBAN fund.

Three kinds of projects have been proposed for the period 1996 to 1999 and were realised thereafter:

- a) Demolition of buildings in the centre of blocks (*Entkernung*) to lower the density and to help create new green open spaces in connection with the rehabilitation of existing dwellings
- b) New construction of buildings and adaptation of vacant ground floors for small enterprises (mixing land uses) compatible with residential areas in connection with sound insulation and greening of roofs
- c) Improvement of public space

As the name of the project suggests, ecological aspects were prominent in the entire program: the objective of a „city of short ways“ is secured by a mixed land use structure and by the block-wise approach. Also the greening of backyards and roofs are part of the philosophy in the same way as the modernization of the technical equipment within the individual dwellings. Local business received logistical assistance and gaps between buildings or minor streets were transformed into attractive public spaces or parks - especially for social groups that were neglected in the past, like older people, children and young people who need room for noisy activities etc.

3.4.2. Objective: Green economy

Internationalization often removes decision making power, even on business matters from the local context and can lead to absurd situations or destroys the local economic base. An example would be if Portugal with a labour intensive traditional wine production was overrun with cheap industrially produced wine from California or from South Africa and local producers cannot compete.

Tool: Local green currency (small is beautiful)

An obvious solution would be some kind of exchange economy for local goods whose values represent the true labour input.

Case study: The Bristol Pound in Britain

Bristol, a European Green Capital Finalist in 2014, suffers from the devaluation of its own labour force after the closing down of its conventional industries. Having lost its stake in the international economy, the city decided to rely on the **green economy**, and has initiated the **Bristol Pound**,¹⁰⁴ a local unit of currency, which is available both on paper and electronically. By encouraging people to use this local form of payment (e.g. via mobile phone), the city gives residents a collective sense of their own city, thus strengthening the local economy.

The Bristol Pound has gained international attention as a flagship local currency, with the aim of keeping money within the city, and supporting the local community

Source: <http://www.thebristolshop.co.uk/products/bristol-pound-souvenir-paper-full-note-set>

TOOL: Playing the globalization game: international awards

If you can't beat them, then join them. International awards usually will give you less direct financial returns than what you invest in the application. But the points

¹⁰⁴ <http://bristolpound.org/> viewed 30/05/2015

earned in publicity can be high and pay back in the long run. Even more important is an award when it comes to convince local politicians about future orientation.

Case study: Copenhagen, European Green Capital 2014

Copenhagen's goal is to become carbon neutral by 2015. The instrument to achieve this is a set of **eight green economy drivers**:

1. **Urban Form** (compact city, finger plan)
2. **Innovation** (education, research and development amounts to 3.1% of national GDP)
3. **High of Foreign Direct Investment** (FDI) amounting to about 50% of GDP.
4. **Skills and Employment** (46% of population with university degree; unemployment rate 2.5% less than European average)
5. **Enterprise** (Copenhagen capital region accounts to 50% of national business exports). The annual growth of the Copenhagen CleanTech sector 2012 was estimated 28% in the combined following sectors:
 - Building efficiency materials
 - Smart grids
 - Clean water
 - Solid waste
 - Clean road transport (electric vehicles and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles)
 - Onshore and offshore wind power generation
 - Solar power capture with photovoltaic cells
 - Geothermal energy
 - Biomass energy (electricity production and biofuel)
6. **Energy and resource efficiency**. (household energy consumption fell by 10% between 2005 and 2011; water consumption fell by 36% [1989/2010]; waste production fell by 19% [2006/2010] with only 2% ending up in landfills)
7. **Low carbon** (district heating expansion and national wind energy deployment allowed to drop carbon emission per inhabitant from 7.9 to 3.2 tonnes 1991/2012). Carbon taxes and subsidies for biomass fuels have made it cost effective for Copenhagen's utilities to shift away from fossil fuels.

Environmental quality (SO₂ pollution fell by 83% 1990/2000; carbon monoxide fell by 72% 2004/2007)

TOOL: Green Banking and Green Bonds¹⁰⁵

Green Bonds are short-hand for Qualified Green Building and Sustainable Design Project Bonds, i.e. a tax-exempt bonds which are issued by federal-qualified organizations and/or municipalities for the development of brownfield sites. The tax-exempt status makes purchasing a green bond a more attractive investment

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.idfc.org/Our-Program/green-finance-mapping.aspx> visited 7/31/2015

when compared to a comparable taxable bond. The public sector can facilitate a bank's development by creating the institutional framework and rules while feeding the institution with public capital can then attract greater shares of private funds. The World Bank has been a leader in the market, and has issued over \$USD 5.3 billion in Green Bonds since an initiating activity in 2008.^{106, 107} The Climate Bonds Initiative, an international NGO, reports that issuances grew by 25% between 2011 and 2012 globally; that the market is overwhelmingly populated by investment grade bonds; and that issuers come from both the municipal, corporate, and institutional sectors

Another option for scaling up the available capital for green technology and infrastructure investments is the creation of a public-private 'Green Bank.' Creating this type of institution can leverage public funds with private sources that are attracted to the long-term returns of infrastructure projects from investors motivated by a low-carbon or green innovation ethos. Pension and insurance funds are often cited as ideal investor candidates.

Case study. Sweden: City of Gothenburg Green Bond¹⁰⁸

In 2013 the City of Gothenburg was the first in the world to introduce green bonds starting with the issue of SEK 500 million and could lead to two billion. In May 2014 there was an announcement of a second bond from the City of Gothenburg. The issue of SEK 1.8 billion (\$273 million) received "tremendous" interest.

The Green Bond Programmes and funds are used primarily to support projects that counter or help adaptation to climate change. For investors there is no difference in credit quality – but a big difference exists in transparency as investors get a picture of what the funding is used for. There is a huge international interest in green bonds reaching up to international agencies, like in the case of Gothenburg opening a bond jointly with the United Nations Environment Programme

¹⁰⁶ <http://www.tbli.org.uk/tbli-conference/news/conferences/will-green-bonds-incentivize-more-direct-investments-perspectives-from-tbli-conference-nordic-2015.html> seen 7/31/2015

¹⁰⁷ <http://www.worldbank.org/content/dam/Worldbank/document/Climate/climate2014-green-bonds-brief-091214.pdf> seen 7/31/2015

¹⁰⁸ http://carbonn.org/uploads/tx_carbonndata/Green%20Bonds.pdf seen 7/31/2015

As part of the environmental programme, the City of Gothenburg continues to issue bonds for financing various environmental projects in the areas of renewable energy, public transport, water treatment, energy efficiency, smart grids, urban planning and waste management. The projects are financed, in whole or in part, by the City of Gothenburg to promote the transition to low carbon dioxide and climate-resilient growth as determined by the City of Gothenburg.

City of Gothenburg was the first city in the world to issue green bonds.

Source: <http://www.lseg.com/markets-products-and-services/our-markets/london-stock-exchange/equities-markets/raising-equity-finance/market-opening-ceremony/welcome-stories/london-stock-exchange-welcomes-city-göthenburg-green-bond>

TOOL: Urban Renewal Funds.

Smaller municipalities and districts, who eventually carry the responsibility for local action, normally don't have the resources to engage in the issue of bonds. Nevertheless, Competition between these institutions to access Urban Renewal Funds issued by large municipalities or governments can work as stimulation to execute sustainable renewal schemes on the local level.

Case Study: Belgium: Flanders Urban Renewal Fund¹⁰⁹

Urban development programs were mostly directed towards poverty reduction until 1999, when a new liberal government won the elections and introduced new policy concepts based on competitiveness and more space for private sector involvement. Since 2002 the Flanders provincial government subsidised urban renew-

¹⁰⁹ http://www.thuisindestad.be/Stadsvernieuwing_6.html seen 7/31/2015

al initiatives in the inner parts of towns, whereby the selection criteria for funding mostly referred to high urban and architectural quality and community participation – all of them subordinated under the abstract principles of competitiveness, safety and quality of life. The financial instruments were the so-called ‘Stedenfonds’, a substantial reserved share within the state budget for which the different municipalities had to enter a stiff competition (typically one winner among three applicants).¹¹⁰ Public private partnership were favoured as applicants, but smaller municipalities could apply for logistical assistance (training, consultancies) in the application phase and before to develop a competitive proposal. Typical project types include conversion of former industrial sites, railway stations, harbours, etc.

To summarize, the provincial government subsidy consisted of three elements:

- a) The actual competition for the urban renewal project
- b) capacity building and consultancies to improve the quality of competition entries
- c) the final awards for the best realization of projects,

3.4.3. Objective: Economic revitalization and stronger global integration

Investors and manufacturers are becoming more and more international and, like tourists, tend to operate between a limited number of ‘global cities’. These are characterised by certain rational characteristics, like proximity to ports and airports, political and urban security, cultural or natural attraction etc. Also simple reference in the news to the city, positive mention in the media, connotation with international events make an indirect contribution to global popularity. Higher ranking on the global cities scale have shown to attract more international investment and/or attraction for tourists. Both imply more jobs locally and higher incomes for the municipality and region.

TOOL: Place branding and iconic architecture

Commercial city marketing, usually referred to as ‘place branding’, actively promote the international reputation of a city – or sometimes of an entire region where individual cities are not strong enough on their own. Apart from world scale events, like Olympic Games or World Exhibitions, an iconic Building designed by a famous architect can have a supporting effect, like the Siney Opera House, the Sony Centre in Berlin and, of course, the Tower Bridge in London or the Eiffel Tower in Paris serve for promotion.

Case Study in Spain: Bilbao – the Guggenheim Museum^{111, 112, 113}

¹¹⁰ <http://www.eib.europa.eu/attachments/documents/jessica-evaluation-study.pdf> visited 23/08/2015

¹¹¹ http://www.bilbao.net/ingles/bilbaonegocios/invertir/eng/1_regeneration.htm viewed 27/05/2015

Bilbao Harbour before urban renewal intervention.

Source; [http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/3624/1/Bilbao_city_report_\(final\).pdf](http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/3624/1/Bilbao_city_report_(final).pdf)

Bilbao – once an important port city and industrial centre for the region - was badly affected by the industrial crisis of the 1970s. Within the metropolitan area, 80,000 jobs in industry were lost. Finally, its politicians, institutions, and citizens decided to switch to delivery of services to become the principal economic activity for Bilbao, offering a high quality of life, turning brown fields into parks and other green infrastructure. The harbour area was to undergo an innovative urban renewal effort that would engage the public interest and make the city more attractive as a site for international forums. New installations include, among others, the Euskalduna Conference Hall, the Airport, the Metro,¹¹⁴ the tramway and the Uribitarte promenade along the Estuary river and of course, the Guggenheim Bilbao Museum – all built by world-renowned architects. The names include Gehry, Foster, Pelli, Legorreta, Isozaki, Calatrava, Sterling, Soriano and others. The Bilbao Renewal Program received the UN Habitat Best Practice award in 2014.¹¹⁵

The most well-known development on the site is the landmark Guggenheim Museum designed by the architect Frank Gehry. The museum opened in 1997 attracting over a million visitors in its first year and it immediately became a major tourist attraction. Bilbao's recovery from industrial decline has by now become one of the most well-known success stories in Europe. It has been said that Bilbao is a city “actively engaging in globalisation strategies and getting transformed in the process”.¹¹⁶

¹¹² <http://urban-complexity.blogspot.de/2010/01/entrepreneurial-urban-regeneration-of.htmlviewd> 27/05/2015

¹¹³ <http://www.bilbao.net/ingles/bilbaonegocios/invertir/pdf/cityforinvestment.pdf> visited 29/05/2015

¹¹⁴ <https://www.metrobilbao.eus/> seen 01/08/2015

¹¹⁵ http://mirror.unhabitat.org/bp/bp.list.details.aspx?bp_id=4737 visited 23/05/2015

¹¹⁶ [http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/3624/1/Bilbao_city_report_\(final\).pdf](http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/3624/1/Bilbao_city_report_(final).pdf). page 27. checked 8/1/2015

<p>Bilbao Metro Entrance designed by William Forster Source: http://micro.com/metro/metroart.html</p>	<p>Bilbao department of Health Source: http://www.fromupnorth.com/archive/architecture/37497/</p>
<p>The Bilbao Arena, designed by Idom architects, UK. Source: http://www.e-architect.co.uk/bilbao/</p>	<p>Guggenheim Museum Bilbao by Frank Gehry. http://quetraman.com/guggenheim-museum-bilbao-architecture.html/</p>

There was also a big increase in airport passengers from 1.4 million in 1994 to 3.8 million in 2005. the sheer scale of added tourist numbers seems certain to have created many smaller service outlets, bars, shops, cafes, small hotels, restaurants, guides, tourist mementos and so on. The indirect knock-on effects in the city are extremely wide if immeasurable, which has been referred to as ‘Guggenheim effect’ on Bilbao’s city economy, which many other cities try to replicate. ‘Due to a successful image change, the city is now internationally recognised as a successful example of urban recovery. Some voices have however criticised the strong focus on urban marketing that prioritises ‘putting the city on the map’, for example the costly subsidies to the city’s only really global attraction, the Guggenheim Museum.’¹¹⁷

New housing was also built to replace the congested living quarters close to river, but criticism was formulated in respect to the low number of flats provided – and even more of the emerging new social segregation pattern created that way. On the positive side it is worth mentioning that the Bilbao Urban renewal effort was able to overcome the burden of administrative fragmentation by founding the development agency Bilbao Ría

¹¹⁷ [http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/3624/1/Bilbao_city_report_\(final\).pdf](http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/3624/1/Bilbao_city_report_(final).pdf), page 35-36. checked 8/1/2015

2000, S.A., to co-ordinate and carry out regeneration initiatives in Bilbao. Set up in November 1992 as a private firm of public shareholders (50 percent central and 50 percent local and regional administration), Ría 2000 operates in practice as a quasi-public agency, a planning and executive body in charge of specific urban renewal operations in the metropolitan area of Bilbao. The Development Corporations were first tested successfully for the New Towns in Britain, like for Milton Keynes.^{118,119}

In sum, the significance of Ría 2000 lies in its considerable potential as a co-ordinating and executive agency and its capacity to act as a unified body in urban redevelopment schemes in metropolitan Bilbao. However, Ría 2000's status as a private firm poses critical questions regarding the 'privatization' of planning and lack of political accountability. Moreover, the imperative of short term profit logic introduces a speculative bend to the agency's operation, which severely undermines its regeneration objectives. If urban regeneration means something more than physical renewal, then equity and redistributive considerations must mediate efficiency criteria.

Fig. 28: Timeline of important events in Bilbao since the late 1970s

Concept and design: J. Plöger

¹¹⁸ <http://www.livingarchive.org.uk/content/local-history/topics/area-development/milton-keynes-development-corporation-1967-1992> visited 23/08/2015

¹¹⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Milton_Keynes_Development_Corporation visited 23/08/2015

Case study Italy; Torino Internazionale and Porta Palazzo Regeneration Area 2001-2006,^{120,121,122}

Located in the North West of Italy, Turin is one of Italy's most industrial cities, known also as the "Italian Detroit" or "one company city". Indeed, until recently, FIAT (car manufacturer), and its automotive industry spin offs, have had a significant impact on urban growth, economic development and social transformations of Turin. FIAT has also been an important social welfare actor in Turin providing housing and a range of social benefits to its workers, most of whom migrated to Turin from impoverished Southern Italian regions after World War II.

Since the mid-1970s FIAT began to shift production out of Turin to regions with lower production costs, which caused a sudden burden of very high unemployment in the city and triggered off further economic and social decline.

<p style="text-align: center;">Employees - Turin Area</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Estimated Employee Numbers in Turin Area (1981-2001)</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Year</th> <th>car industry</th> <th>business & services</th> <th>textile industry</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1981</td> <td>135,000</td> <td>130,000</td> <td>28,000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1991</td> <td>105,000</td> <td>140,000</td> <td>20,000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2001</td> <td>60,000</td> <td>125,000</td> <td>10,000</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Year	car industry	business & services	textile industry	1981	135,000	130,000	28,000	1991	105,000	140,000	20,000	2001	60,000	125,000	10,000	
Year	car industry	business & services	textile industry														
1981	135,000	130,000	28,000														
1991	105,000	140,000	20,000														
2001	60,000	125,000	10,000														
<p>Loss of employment in Torino 1981-2001</p> <p>Source: http://trends.gmfus.org/doc/Torino%20-%20Corsico.pdf</p>	<p>Former FIAT car factories in Torino,</p> <p>Source: http://www.accessibilityplanning.eu/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/2012-Torino-Franco-Corsico-et-Matteo-Tabasso-Turin-Urban-and-Transport-Transformation-Turin-16-02-2012.pdf</p>																

In 1999, accepting the need for an economic paradigm shift, the city managed to secure hosting the 2006 Winter Olympic Games which marked a turning-point in its regeneration trajectory, with a growing emphasis being laid by local politico-economic elites on internationalization and inter-city competition. Relying on the so-called 'Barcelona effect',¹²³

¹²⁰ <http://www.accessibilityplanning.eu/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/2012-Torino-Franco-Corsico-et-Matteo-Tabasso-Turin-Urban-and-Transport-Transformation-Turin-16-02-2012.pdf> accessed 01/08/2015

¹²¹

http://www.innovateballymun.org/sites/default/files/socialinnovation/Social%20Sustainabilityand%20Urban%20Regenerationreport_0.pdf visited 18/05/2015

¹²² <http://trends.gmfus.org/doc/Torino%20-%20Corsico.pdf>

¹²³ With reference to the Barcelona Olympic games in 1992. See also:

<https://www.bostonglobe.com/sports/2014/11/26/barcelona-olympic-makeover-may-hold-lessons-for-boston/d8TNfL0oTbtJwiR4vE1NLL/story.html> ; <http://www.businessinsider.com/how-the-olympic-games-changed-barcelona-forever-2012-7?IR=T> visited 23.08.2015

the Olympic games were seen as an opportunity for urban change, the urban landscape was enriched with futuristic buildings designed by renowned architects, while the construction of a new subway line revolutionized the city's transportation network. Turin was given the chance start its 'second life'.

Also following the Barcelona recipe, Turin was the first city in Italy to adopt an urban strategic plan.¹²⁴ The adoption of a strategic rationale for urban planning introduced a process of re-scaling the city's identity while consolidating its international connections at the same time. A public-private partnership led by the municipality and the provincial government with the involvement of local companies, private foundations and entrepreneurial organizations gave rise to Torino Internazionale, a formalized coalition aimed at creating a shared vision for enhancing the city's competitiveness in a context of globalization. The renovation of the historic centre has been at the heart of the process of Turin's widely celebrated renaissance. Those working class neighbourhoods still suffered a lot from the economic crisis and were stigmatized by assumed high level of crime and a predominantly immigrant population.

Urban renewal and revitalization programs were launched and also included reinforcing the social texture in urban semi-central neighbourhoods such as Porta Palazzo the centrally located open market – the biggest in Europe – by making use of extraordinary public and even EU funds. Also the former industrial site close to the city centre was transformed through a public-private enterprise. The master plan was imitating a historical city texture while the individual buildings were designed by some of the most famous international architects of the time. The Porta Palazzo quarter has become an international show piece project without any further social ambitions.

<p><i>Porta Palazzo – Europe's biggest open air market</i></p>	<p><i>Regional Government of Piermont in Turin. Source:</i></p>

¹²⁴ <http://www.uclg.org/en/issues/urban-strategic-planning> visited 23.08.2015

Source: http://www.coopsette.it/files/coopsette/piemonte_gallery.jpg	http://www.coopsette.it/files/coopsette/piemonte_gallery.jpg
<p>Torino art Gallery – extension designed by Renzo Piano, 2002</p> <p>Source: http://content-artshub-com-au.s3.amazonaws.com/contentimages/3JAN2014/1-.jpg</p>	<p>Urban tree house in Torino, Italy</p> <p>Source: http://www.skyscrapercity.com/showthread.php?p=122864351</p>

TOOL: Green business and leadership

Economic successes in navigating a city within the ocean of global economy merit recognition but do not necessarily contribute to the reduction of global warming. Ecological approaches to urban economies rather suggest a certain independence from global markets but still need income levels to cover all operational costs and redemption.

Case Study Italy: Varese Ligure 1995^{125, 126}

The Italian municipality Varese Ligure is small but the lessons it can teach the world are very exciting. At the end of the 1980s, the municipality's population had diminished from 6,000 to 2,250 citizens, due to a lack of jobs, no industry, decaying properties, and a lack of essential services. The municipality was geographically isolated, it had a lack of modern industry, and the farming practices were antiquated. Then the new mayor at the time, Maurizio Caranza, refused to give up and drew up a recovery plan which, with the active support of the residents, was then put into practice from 1990 onwards.

Since the municipality was falling apart, an agreement was reached between the municipality and the citizens. The municipality was to organize funding for upgrading the urban infrastructure, partly with EU assistance, and the community would take care of renovating their own old houses. The deal worked out and became the base for future production initiatives – basically relying on organic farming and renewable energies.

¹²⁵ <http://www.dac.dk/en/dac-cities/sustainable-cities/all-cases/master-plan/small-italian-municipality-sets-an-example-for-the-worlds-cities/> seen 8/1/2015

¹²⁶ <http://www.renewableenergyworld.com/articles/2007/12/renewable-energy-powers-italian-town-and-its-economy-50863.html> seen 8/2/2015

<p>Varese Figure: Village core Source: http://www.leduepoiane.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/06/download-2.jpg</p>	<p>Varese Figure: facades http://metaefficient.com/wp-content/uploads/2007/12/varese_lecture.jpg</p>

Since 1996, an Environmental Education Center (CEA) educates the local young generation about organic agriculture, renewable energy, and sustainability. Also courses are provided about energy consumption and climate change. Organic farming practices were taught to the local farmers, who couldn't afford chemical fertilizers anyway: in practice they were already organic, but they weren't officially certified. With EU grants for organic farms, they became interested in certifying the farms as organic. Today there are 108 organic farms that supply 98% of the municipality's produce, including organic porcini mushrooms, chestnuts, cheeses, honey, fruit, vegetables, meat and dairy products. Good restaurants opened. Artists and craftspeople arrived. The Vara valley is now known as the "Organic Valley", and in 1999 it became Europe's first valley to be certified for environmental management under ISO 14001.

To supply the municipality with renewable electricity, four wind turbines were installed on a ridge 1,100 meters above sea level. These turbines generate 8 million kWh of electricity per year: three times the amount needed by the municipality; the surplus is fed into the local grid. The municipality hall and the secondary school roofs are covered by solar photovoltaic panels, which supply 98% and 62% of their electricity needs, respectively. This output is complemented by a number of small-scale hydropower generators – and the municipal piscine is directly heated through solar collectors. The shift to renewable energy has added 140 jobs and added an additional \$514,000 USD in annual tax revenues for the municipality. Last but not least, the success of this village development, together with the UN HABITAT awarded in 2014, helped to increase the number of visiting tourists by 500% since the late 1990s, many coming just to see the renewable energy achievements.

<p>Varese autonomous energy supply Source: http://3.bp.blogspot.com/_HFeJw58JbFs/TAN_tnO7hSI/AAAAAAAAA1A/nqb8-wRwVvU/s1600/wind+power.jpg</p>	<p>Organic Food Festival in Varese Source: http://www.animalieanimali.it/rubriche/31538_a_varese_ligure_arriva_il_primo_festival_del_bio</p>

TOOL: Mix of several land uses

Replacing old and decaying old housing stock and building fresh again can be more economical than renewal– especially on virgin land at the outskirts of the city where land prices are more economical. However, considering all monetary and other costs, it makes more sense to densify inner city areas since the urban infrastructures already exist, the distances are shorter and the urban footprint is reduced. This is particularly true when different land uses are combined as the time and transportation needs are less (city of short ways).

Case study:Vienna ecological block renewal 1996^{127, 128}

"Ecological Block Renewal" is a key project of the Viennese urban renewal strategy. It is partly financed through the Vienna Land Procurement and Urban Renewal Fund (WBSF) and combined the aims of the older soft urban renewal policy with ecological measures but also includes fostering local business apart from only housing improvements. It particularly addresses those urban quarters constructed at the turn of the century (1900) situated along the western Guertel road where the blocks are densely built up. The technical equipment of houses in these areas is still very poor. In addition, there is a significant lack of green spaces and the unemployment rate is higher than the Viennese average which justifies the use of public subsidies.

¹²⁷ http://mirror.unhabitat.org/bp/bp.list.details.aspx?bp_id=2402 accessed 22/05/2015

¹²⁸

<https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=images&cd=&ved=0CAUQjhxqFQoTCKvBxs7e4cYCFVER2wodARsDsQ&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.wohnbauforschung.at%2Findex.php%3Finc%3Ddownload%26id%3D5552&ei=rrouVauyN9HW7AaBtoyICw&psig=AFQjCNH48hUFBXsG6Aa liaSBYqRK4cdaGg&ust=1437207782757146> accessed 17/07/2015

Single measures transforming one or several neighbouring houses are preferred to entire blocks because this approach is expected to have optimum benefits with low expenses at the same time. Apart from that of the fragmented ownership structures would make entire block renewal very complicated and time consuming. Each funded project may receive a maximum 30 % financial contribution for all expenses from the European Union URBAN fund. Ecological aspects are followed by securing a mixed land-use structure and the greening of backyards and roofs are part of this philosophy. In most cases there is a combination of improving the technical equipment of dwellings, measures for local business and steps toward more attractive public spaces - including gaps between buildings or minor streets. Projects which improve the situation for hence neglected social groups are given special attention, like close-by parks for the elderly or playgrounds for children and young people who need room for noisy activities etc

Technically speaking, three kinds of projects were earmarked in particular:

- Demolition of buildings in the centre of blocks (*Entkernung*) in order to lower the density and to help create new green open spaces in connection with the rehabilitation of existing dwellings
- New construction of buildings and adaptation of vacant ground floors for small enterprises (mixing land uses) compatible with residential areas in connection with sound insulation and greening of roofs
- Improvement of public spaces

3.5 Strategy: Social Sustainability

The well-being of a neighbourhood depends on the interplay between its physical, economic and social structures. If the residents are poor, they cannot maintain their dwellings. If they lack skills and education or if they are stigmatized they may find it more difficult to find employment or earn an honest income otherwise. If the buildings are in a poor estate, the residents may suffer stigmatization etc. Therefore it is essential to look at a neighbourhood with a comprehensive understanding – otherwise no renewal program can be sustainable.

3.5.1 Objective: access to *adequate shelter*

For the residents the ultimate objective of urban renewal schemes is the creation and adaptation of adequate living space, of which housing, though not exclusively, is the principal element. The perceived lack of housing units usually is the leading argument, although the official numbers tell very little. Size, location and typology may be inadequate but can be adapted – which is also true for the problem of affordability.

TOOL: Neighbourhood contracts and other governmental subsidy schemes

Almost all European urban renewal and revalorization schemes imply subsidies in which the state attempts to rectify defects in past and current housing and urban policies or practices. The subsidy programs usually reflect the changing ideologies of the state, which in Europe tend to be determined by the political parties in power.

Case study Brussels: Sustainable Neighbourhood Contracts 1989¹²⁹

Faced with significant problems of physical and socio-economic decay in the centre and the older suburban areas, the Brussels Capital Region has been implementing an integrated renewal and development policy for deprived neighbourhoods. The major instrument in this revitalisation policy is the Neighbourhood Contract. A Neighbourhood contract must define a clearly limited area, address housing provision, the renovation of buildings or public spaces, but also include socio-economic actions, like the setting up, or remodelling of infrastructure or services (social, cultural, sporting and others), at the local or district level.

A neighbourhood contract proposal is normally written by a consultant under the supervision of the local authority. To ensure that the programme best meets the needs of the district, the Commune has to organise ways in which the people who live, work and visit the district are kept informed and involved. Operations deal with three large action areas – housing, public spaces and socio-economic development. Actions may consist of:

- upgrading existing housing;
- creating new housing units;
- upgrading or creating spaces reserved for handicraft or industrial activities, associated with complementary housing initiatives;
- refurbishing public spaces;
- creation or upgrading of the infrastructure and equipment present in the district, whether socio-cultural, sporting or other;
- setting up social and economic activities

The formal contract is signed between the Brussels regional government and the eligible districts of execution, which must belong to list of neighbourhoods in deprivation. This list includes 13.8% of the capital region or 30% of its population. More than 50% of the funds were in-

¹²⁹ <http://www.quartiers.irisnet.be/>

vested in (mostly social) house building or improvement, 20% for upgrading of public space, about 25% for socio-economic measures.

Since 2010 also measures to reduce climate change can be financed. Individual house owners can also apply for improvement grants funded from a different source. Remarkable is the high degree of community participation in all measures of the program. The rotating principle in the distribution of funds assures a wide coverage within the region and avoids the nutrition of a customary grant recipient mentality.

<p>Participation is part of the Neighbourhood Contract Source: http://www.quartiers.irisnet.be/</p>	<p>Invitation for a public hearing for the neighbourhood contract Source: http://www.quartiers.irisnet.be/</p>
<p>Proposal for improvement in the Albert "Dalle" quarter Source: http://quartieralbertwijk.blogspot.de</p>	<p>Apartment house renovated by neighbourhood contract Source: http://www.25ans-sprb.irisnet.be/25ans/Rapport25ans-FR.html</p>

TOOL: Adaptation of unpopular mass housing typology

Particularly uniform mass housing estates can become unpopular with its residents and turn into ghettos of the disadvantaged who don't have the means or connections to transfer to other neighbourhoods or typologies. Physical transformation of those housing blocks can be a solution.

Case study Leinefelde in East Germany: House type adaptation, 2004^{130,131,132}

¹³⁰ http://www.baunetzwissen.de/objektartikel/Altbaumodernisierung_Rueckbau-einer-Plattenbauzeile-in-Leinefelde_69134.html, visited 04/06/2015

In Leinefelde, Eastern Germany, massive prefabricated housing blocks had been built for the workers of a huge factory which closed down soon after reunification of Germany and the former workers left looking for jobs in West Germany. This process called for partial demolition of the prefabricated large panel housing blocks and transformation of the remaining structure into highly attractive town houses with more popular floor plans, gardens, balconies and rooftop terraces. At the same time, modern energy saving standards have been achieved though 10cm external wall insulation (20cm roof insulation) and new double glazing windows. Existing district heating is relatively inexpensive but heat losses remain a problem during the summer months when the entire system must be kept operational for hot water supply.

Case Study; Berlin Marzahn 1970/ 1990/ 2000/ 2005¹³³

Marzahn is Germany's largest housing estate with originally more than 58,000 units built 1977 – 1989, which suffered increasing problems of under-occupation after reunification due to its negative social image, low technical standards and its peripheral location in respect to the now united Berlin. Given the predictable medium and long term need for housing in the united German capital, a combination of new building, remodelling, renovation and partial demolition was chosen and successfully applied to turning Marzahn into an attractive quarter again - with only about 5% availability of empty flats (normal fluctuation rate). Adding extensive recreation areas the suburb was marketed as a 'Garden City within the Metropole'. The monotonous architecture was given a facelift by employing architects from other continents to guide the renovation and to create,

¹³¹ http://www.leinefelde-worbis.de/stadtumbau/files/publish/Energiegerechte_Sanierung_DETAIL_Buch_07.pdf visited 04/06/2015

¹³² http://www.leinefelde-worbis.de/stadtumbau/files/publish/DArchitektenblattOST_4_2007.pdf viewed 04/06/2015

¹³³ http://www.staedtebaufoerderung.info/StBauF/DE/Programm/StadtumbauOst/Praxis/Massnahmen/Marzahn/Marzahn_node.html

for example, a 'Brazilian Quarter' or a Japanese Garden'. Some houses were especially adapted for the needs of old age residents, with medical surgeries attached and a formal reception desk ('concierge') at the entry downstairs.

<p>Berlin Marzahn overview</p>	
<p>Marzahn-Ahrensfelder Terrassen after renewal (top and left) Source: IRS Erkner</p>	<p>Marzahn Chinese garden Source: http://www.euromag.ru/specprojects/routes-of-berlin/29284.html</p>

3.5.2 Objective: Tackling the land question

When it comes to discussing housing affordability and location, the cost of the land invariably turns out to be the key issue. Differential land values fuel social segregation, and land speculation makes decent housing unaffordable even to middle income groups in major urban centres. Since more than a hundred years different reformers have tried to find a solution to this problem, or at least a way to combat excesses of land speculation.

Tool: Cooperative housing

Land speculation tends to be perpetuated in conditions where housing property changes hands between different occupants a dwelling. But similar as in the classic government owned social housing schemes, a permanent ownership can be achieved in certain types of housing cooperatives in which its members are not allowed to materialize increased land values when moving flats.

Case study München: Wagnis eG 2005^{134, 135}

In Munich, the city with highest rent levels in Germany, this cooperative has opted the third tenure apart from renting and outright ownership. By now, it has already build four passive-energy housing projects on brown field sites. Apart from promoting cooperative as an instrument to release more urban land from speculative property market, an ambitious set of social and ecological aims could be realised by this group. Since the termination of the pioneer project in 2005, two other housing estates have been built by the same cooperative in Munich. The project won the Cooperative Award for housing in 2010.

3.5.3 Objective: Location and ease of mobility

Poorer people are more dependent on mobility since they are less likely to afford individual transport (at least in cold climates) – either own or hired – and they find it more difficult to find a new or first home after accepting a workplace far away from their previous residence.

TOOL: Better and affordable public transport

Transportation is expensive and if several family members of less affluent families need to move for work or education this may imply a substantial share of their household income. Therefore urban renewal needs to take the mobility question into consideration – especially keeping in mind that a considerable part of the population, like old age persons, handicapped and children cannot switch to car, bicycles or hiking.

Case Study: Talinin, Estonia **Ticket-free public transport** 2013^{136, 137}

¹³⁴ <http://www.rohn-verlag.de/26.html> viewed 23/05/2015

¹³⁵ <http://www.wagnis.org/genossenschaft.0.html> viewed 23/05/2015

The 400,000 inhabitants-city Talinin decided upon the introduction of **ticket-free public transportation**, not only to stimulate car drivers to switch to public transport, but also to improve social cohesion. Although time is needed to evaluate if the anticipated amount of car drivers really switch to public transport, the measure also aims to improve social cohesion through offering equal mobility opportunities for all strata of society. Improved social welfare, safer and calmer streets and cleaner air - this is what the local municipality hopes to achieve with this measure.

<p>Bus in Tallinn costs zero fare for residents</p> <p>Source: http://citiscopescope.org/sites/default/files/styles/story_large/public/Passengers-go-on-the-bus-in-the-center-of-Tallinn-sm.jpg?itok=nWQMhX2m</p>	<p>Tallinn – Capital of Free Public Transport</p> <p>Source: http://farefreepublictransport.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/09/tallinn-600x400.jpg</p>

A considerable number of other European, North American and Brazilian cities also operate or consider free fare public transportation systems.¹³⁶ In all places the success in attracting passengers was overwhelming, in some cases more than 10-fold and more (In Lemgo, Germany, the increase was even 50-fold from 40,000 to 2 million plus passengers per year!), which creates a challenge to the economic feasibility of the scheme for the municipalities. Now several cities, including Berlin, propose a mandatory flat rate for all citizens who may work out at €1,- per day.¹³⁹

Case study: Tramway revival in France and other cities¹⁴⁰

Having scrapped tramways in the 1950s, the first French towns to reintroduce trams in the mid- 1980s, were Nantes and then Grenoble. Usually this measure went hand-in-hand with major urban renewal schemes to help the local population to accept their reappearance on the streets. Tramways are a means of transport which offer certain proven advantages:

- a capacity beyond 3,000 passengers per hour per direction of travel;

¹³⁶ <http://www.eltis.org/discover/news/free-public-transport-tallinn-estonia-0>, seen 8/2/2015
¹³⁷ <http://citiscopescope.org/story/2014/free-public-transit-tallinn-hit-riders-yields-unexpected-results> seen 8/2/2015
¹³⁸ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Free_public_transport
¹³⁹ DieTageszeitung. 30.May 2015, Kontext Supplement page 2.
¹⁴⁰ http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/11001-2_Renouveau-tramway-France_GB.pdf reviewed 25/05/2015

- an average commercial speed of 18-22 km/h;
- a regular transport service;
- a high level of comfort;
- optimal accessibility;
- enjoying daylight and smooth movement (for reading)
- lower cost than an underground system: an average cost of 13-22 million Euros per km for the transport component in France.

Currently, 27 French urban areas have at least one tramway line. Trams have also become a tool for promoting a town, because building a tramway implies a desire to renew the image of the town where it is located.

In 2007, the French state launched the Environment roundtable to draw up a French road map for ecology, sustainable development and planning. Within this framework the state plans to achieve a target of 1,800 km of tram lines by 2020. In May 2010, the state made 590 million euros available to support 78 new projects backed by 54 transport management authorities: 45 high service level buses, 29 tramways, 2 underground systems and 2 sea links. Nearly 1,000 km of lines will already have been built or launched by late 2013. Tramways reshape the urban landscape.

TOOL: pro-cycling planning and infrastructure

On short to medium distance trips in town, say from 0,5 to 5km, the bicycle is still the fastest and certainly most ecological means of transport. It is non-polluting and in addition keeps the body fit. Local governments can do a lot to encourage the use of bicycles but also to protect cyclists from accidents

Traffic accidents with bodily harm

Source; www.copenhagenize.com seen 8/2/2015

Case Study Copenhagen City of cyclists^{141, 142}

Every day people cycle 1.2 million km in Copenhagen, while thousands of people travel by bus, train, and underground or on foot. Copenhagen is in the midst of a historic expansion of its public transport system, and there has been massive investment in more cycle-only paths, bridges and underpasses. Good conditions for cycling are also part of the city's official health policy. The number of kilometres cycled has risen by around 30% since 1998 and the bicycle's modal share for trips to work or educational institutions has also risen to over a third in the same period. This makes the bicycle the most popular transport form for commuting in Copenhagen. Copenhageners choose the bicycle because it's the fastest and easiest way to get around.

¹⁴¹ <http://www.copenhagenize.com>, visited 8/2/2015

¹⁴² <http://denmark.dk/en/green-living/bicycle-culture/> visited 8/2/2015

Source; <http://www.cycling-embassy.dk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/2011-2013-Fact-sheet-cycling-in-DK-1.pdf>

embassy.dk/2013/05/22/bicycles-in-the-media/

The pro-cycling planning policy involves in particular the provision of more space to cyclists on the main arteries and to improving cycling travel times through short cuts like tunnels and bridges over water, railways and large roads. In addition, it requires many small speed improvements, such as allowing contra-flow cycling on one-way streets, allowing cycling across squares, implementing more Green Waves for cyclists with traffic lights, etc. Also traffic calming for cars increases the comparative advantage for bicycles. Statistically, the risk of being involved in a serious accident has fallen by 72% per cycled. kilometre since 1996.

Case study Coty of Münster, 'German bicycle capital'^{143,144,145}

¹⁴³ <http://www.muenster.de/stadt/tourismus/en/city-of-bikes.html> seen 28/05/2015

¹⁴⁴ http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:Fahrradstadt_M%C3%BCnster?uselang=de seen 04/06/2015

¹⁴⁵ http://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Radverkehr_in_M%C3%BCnster seen 04/06/2015

The bicycle is the most commonly used means of transport in the small town of Münster, Germany. A daily total of more than 100,000 people travel the roads by bike, and there are twice as many bicycles than residents, namely 500,000. Special facilities include 300 km of designated bicycle paths, preference at traffic lights, 3,500 parking lots for bikes have been provided just alone at the railway station. Münster has won awards for its high share of bicycle trips which amount to more than 37.6% of all trips – the highest in 2007.

At the same time, Münster also suffers the highest rate of bicycle thefts among all German speaking countries. Münster police is tough on bicycle infractions, up to taking your driving licence in heavy cases or drunk driving. Nevertheless Münster continues to win numerous awards for being bicycle friendly.

Bicycle parking in Münster, Germany

Source: <http://www.merkur-online.de>

TOOL: Pedestrianization

Although pedestrian streets are now a very common feature in main shopping areas all over Europe, a lot needs to be done in secondary streets where motor vehicles still enjoy far reaching preference even where they represent a clear minority in numbers. To make things even worse, there is a tendency in some commercial zones and in public transport installations to remove existing benches or other horizontal surfaces to inhibit comfortable resting for non-consumers out of an irrational phobia against possibly appearing vagrants or drunkards.

Case study: Frankfurt and greening of High Street Zeil

The **Zeil** is the traditional high street in the city centre of [Frankfurt, Germany](#). The name, which dates back to the 14th century, is derived from

the German word *Zeile* 'row' and originally referred to a row of houses on the eastern end of the north side; the name was not extended to the entire street until much later.

Since the end of the 19th century it has been one of the most famous and busiest shopping streets in Germany. Before [World War II](#) it was also known for its grand buildings, but most of them were destroyed and not rebuilt. Representing on the first main street in Europe, Zeil was partly pedestrianised as early as 1972, but improved with tree planting above the underground railway in 1983, before it finally underwent a major renovation in 2008/09 with an extension of the pedestrian zone. This brought about a drastic shift in traffic modal split from individual motorized mobility to mass public transport whose main interchange is underneath Hauptwache at the Western end of Zeil which is now completely closed for individual traffic

<p>Frankfurt High Street 'Zeil' in the 1960s</p> <p>Source: http://motorbloeckchen.com/wp-content/uploads/1960-er-Zeil-mit-Strassenbahnen.jpg</p>	<p>Frankfurt Zeil transformed and arborised in 2010</p> <p>Source: http://www.ichliebefrankfurt.de/?id=42457#42457</p>

TOOL: Integrated mobility concept

In those cases where an urban renewal scheme suggests a change in the mobility modal split, this plan will only function if alternatives to the current situation are offered, and the attractiveness of the favoured solution is increased. Therefore public transport, road and parking planning, pricing etc. need to be well synchronized.

Case Study: Hamburg HafenCity development

The first step to facilitate mobility in the new quarter in place of the old harbour is the fine tuned interweaving of different land uses – living – working – culture – leisure – commerce, which minimizes the distances and reduced the transportation needs. The envisaged modal split reduces the habitual individual car use from 74% to 20%. All public parking lots are connected to an electronic guidance system to avoid unnecessary cruising for an empty parking lot – 30% of them equipped with fast currency charging facilities for electric cars – which are also available as part of the quarter-wide car sharing scheme. The electrical cars also serve as buffer-energy storage for the district heating-plus-energy power plant. A new metro line was built to connect the new quarter with the rest of the

city and will be able to move 35,000 passengers daily. Public transport is complemented by several hydrogen powered bus lines and three piers for fetching the water taxis. Several bicycle lending stations have been installed. 70% of pedestrian and cyclist connections are independent (and undisturbed by) car traffic, 30% are located along the river banks.

<p>70% of all footpaths and bicycle ways are separated from car traffic Source: http://www.hafencity.com/upload/images/ImageGallery/z_galerien_en_6_5.jpg</p>	<p>30% of foot and bicycle paths follow the river shore Source: http://www.hamburg.de/contentblob/4328690/data/minidways-tour-bild-2.jpg</p>

3.5.4 Objective: Poverty alleviation

TOOL: Urban renewal programs targeting the poorest neighbourhoods

Upgrading a poor neighbourhood, frequently facing a suspicious community, requires extra public relation resources which often are not available in conventional urban renewal programs. This way, the neediest population is easily left out unless special programs are targeting this problem.

Case Study Ireland. National RAPID programme, 2001^{146,147,148,149}

The programme ‘*Revitalising Areas by Planning, Investment and Development*’ (RAPID) is aimed at improving the quality of life and employment opportunities for residents of the most disadvantaged communities in Irish cities and towns. It aims, in a focused and practical way, to reduce the deprivations commonly faced by residents of disadvantaged communities. It attempts to do this through targeting significant state resources at the needs of disadvantaged areas. Intertwined problems characterise the addressed communities suffering from personal and social deficits – also including the vicious circle of poverty:

- a lack of income;
- a lack of respect between generations;
- pockets of criminal activity;
- vandalism including destruction of public and private property.

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.pobal.ie/FAQ/Pages/RAPID.aspx> viewed 8/3/2015

¹⁴⁷ <http://www.westmeathcoco.ie/en/media/What%20is%20RAPID.pdf> viewed 04/06/2015

¹⁴⁸ <http://www.clarecoco.ie/community/rapid/> viewed 04/06/2015

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.pobal.ie/Beneficiaries/RAPID/Pages/default.aspx> viewed 04/06/2015

The residents of those quarters often also witness other forms of negative and destructive behaviour towards self and others, ranging from depression, addiction, self-harm, suicide, lack of constancy, inability to negotiate and participate, anti-social behaviour, family and social violence, physical and sexual abuse and antagonism towards neighbours and members of the general public. The rapid RAPID program aims to address these problems by

- increasing the investment made by Government departments and state agencies in the 46 communities;
- Improving the delivery of public services through integration and co-ordination
- Enhancing the opportunities for communities to participate in the strategic improvement of their areas.

The programme also offers additional facilities and services and/or re-design current facilities and services so that they are better equipped to the needs of the community. The programme works within a community development approach where the full participation of the community is seen as essential in order to: (a) increase the quantity and quality of public goods and (b) enhance the capacity for self-organising and self-advocacy of individuals, families and community. More concrete examples of public goods and public services provided within RAPID include, among others:

- **environmental goods** (development and maintenance of green spaces, public buildings, the appearance of houses, the removal of litter and rubbish)
- **public safety** (road alignment, traffic calming, regular patrols, protection of residents, parking, CCTV addressing anti-social behaviour, personal visits to re- assure older people)
- **cultural, sport and recreational facilities** (community venues, all weather floodlit facilities, playgrounds, games pitches)
- **transport** (extending public and community transport facilities)
- **family support** (parental involvement, family relationships, addressing addiction, dealing with disruptive behaviour, providing home support systems)
- **education** (school retention and performance, adult and life-long learning)
- **health promotion** (community and personal health strategies for all age groups)
- **enhancing the capacity of individuals**, families and the community
- **stimulating participation** in cultural, social, political, sporting and leisure activities

The RAPID programme started 2001 in 51 neighbourhoods and has been combined with the larger network of 54 local development companies all over the country.

The Ballybane Neighbourhood Revitalization project in Ireland, part of the RAPID program, became finalist for UN-HABITAT Award 2007.

<http://www.worldhabitatawards.org/winners-and-finalists/project-details.cfm?lang=00&theProjectID=7464F17B-15C5-F4C0-9921E2F781A6B235>

Case Study Germany: Social City Programme (Soziale Stadt) 2000^{150, 151}

This program integrates the efforts of various departments and administrative levels in German municipalities in order to tackle the complex issues of urban development programmes in neighbourhoods and quarters with ‘specific needs’. It aims at *physical and social* “rehabilitation” at the same time but is extremely flexible in respect to the measures to be taken. Social segregation can be an issue to address. The funding proposals have to demonstrate the need for a complex urban development and also need to present a detailed plan of planned and integrated measures. So far (2013) a total 617 areas had been included in the program, distributed between 378 German municipalities

Soziale Stadt Program in Worms, Germany

Source: <http://www.worms.de/de-wAssets/img/mein->

Playground developed within the framework of The Social City

Source: <http://baubeconstadtsanierung.de/wp->

¹⁵⁰http://www.innovateballymun.org/sites/default/files/socialinnovation/Social%20Sustainabilityand%20Urban%20Regenerationreport_0.pdf, page 34. visited 18/05/2015

Andrea Colantonio and Tim Dixon: 2009. Measuring Socially Sustainable Urban Regeneration in Europe. Oxford Brookes University, Oxford.

http://www.innovateballymun.org/sites/default/files/socialinnovation/Social%20Sustainabilityand%20Urban%20Regenerationreport_0.pdf visited 18/05/2015

¹⁵¹ http://www.staedtebauforderung.info/StBauF/DE/Programm/SozialeStadt/soziale_stadt_node.html accessed 22/05/2015

Case Study Dortmund Clarenberg, Social City Program 1992^{152,153,154}

Around 1970, a large housing estate with buildings up to 17 floors high had been constructed in Dortmund with the purpose to house more than 3,000 people in social housing units. Twenty years later, a high percentage of unemployed or low-salary tenants combined with high fluctuation rates exposed serious social problems within the estate which called for urgent action on behalf of the municipality. A first and mostly physical improvement program started in 1992 and continued until 1998.

After the estate had been sold to a commercial property company as result of a neo-liberal housing policy shift, Clarenberg was included in the Social City Program which promoted environmental improvement and a large number of social sub-projects. For example, 8 meters high house numbers were placed in front of the entrances understood as pieces of art, care takers named 'Concierges' were sitting at reception desks in the lobby but also helped with minor repairs. Even if the financial situation of the residents may not have improved, the social problems were alleviated and even the social stigma that was attached to the housing estate before renovation was overcome. It is interesting to observe that a simple measure like new clothing for the tower blocks can help to dilute stigmatization if is accompanied with an adequate social works programme.

Dortmund Clarenberg after revalorization program

<https://www.ruhrnachrichten.de/staedte/dortmund/44263-H%F6rde~/Hochhaussiedlung-am-Clarenberg-Architekt-Andreas-Hanke-ueber-sein-Viertel;art2575,987982>

Dortmund Clarenberg House Entries after revalorization program

http://www.brandeins.de/fileadmin/_processed_/csm_126_133_L1045312_ef60c6f26e.jpg

TOOL: Income generation programs

The formal labour market prefers applications from people who already have relevant work experience. This makes it very difficult to find employment for young people who are just entering the job market. However, many of those applicants

¹⁵² <http://www.rohn-verlag.de/26.html> veiwed23/05/2015

¹⁵³ http://www.soziale-stadt.nrw.de/stadtteile_projekte/profil.php?st=dortmund-clarenberg

¹⁵⁴ <http://www.brandeins.de/wissen/bo-city-of-wood/ein-ganz-einfacher-trick/>

are very talented and imaginative – a capital which can be exploited. In urban renewal schemes, the provision of cheap work space is an asset which may be developed into a busy start-up economy nucleus. In many cities empty ware houses have been adapted to provide such opportunities, with the rent covered through a subsidy for the first couple of years.

Case study: CUCULA in Berlin, Germany¹⁵⁵

In response to the increasingly critical situation of African refugees who have arrived in Berlin, the *Internationale JugendKunst- und Kulturhaus* started an initiative providing ‘shelter against the cold’. Among the first beneficiaries, five young men from West Africa obtained accommodation and started to construct the needed furniture on their own to equip their rooms. This marks the birth of CUCULA. The CUCULA Refugees Company for Crafts and Design is a model operation empowering refugees to earn their income and build their own career. As a factory for design furniture CUCULA creates training programmes, thereby creating real prospects. The CUCULA furniture pieces are not only design classics, they also represent the stories of their makers. The 19 DIY furniture design plans from Enzo Mari’s book ‘Autoprogettazione’ in 1974 mark an important milestone in the history of product design. Positioned in contrast to the formalism of the time, Enzo Mari suggests the democratization of design, provoking a stronger identification with our own furniture and fostering a learning and reflection process. 40 years later Enzo Mari grants the team of CUCULA the rights to sell furniture based on his plans.

CUCULA found accommodation in a former ware house belonging to an industrial revitalization zone on the banks of Spree river in Berlin, which 10 years ago has been converted into an international youth art and culture centre which is a registered non-profit organization supported by funding from Berlin based companies, the municipality and individuals.

<p>CUCULA Office, Berlin. Photo: FredMoseley</p>	<p>CUCULA team, Berlin Photo: Verena Brüning</p>	<p>CUCULA production, Berlin, Germany Photo: Bambino</p>
<p>Source: http://www.cucula.org</p>		

¹⁵⁵ <http://www.cucula.org/en/> , <http://www.schlesische27.de/wp/weltkiosk/> visited 24/08/2015

TOOL: Neighbourhood service centres

Public institutions can be a great thing and are supposed to assist the resident population who pays for them anyway through their taxes. But often they maintain a bureaucratic tenure, are accommodated far away from their clientele in some institutional premises with annoying opening hours and possibly staff exposing quite a hostile tune. Fortunately a new generation of ‘real’ public service centres are popping up, often located right within socially critical urban renewal settings, where citizens are not sent from one office to another but find all type of assistance underneath one roof and can even turn up at late hours. Under the same roof you may also find innovative interpretations of public libraries, where you can watch videos, take the books to the coffee shop or can take evening classes. Obviously, kids from less educational family background feel more attracted to these establishments than to classical borough libraries, and will voluntarily learn ‘the easy way’.

Case Study: London: *Idea Stores* - culture-led revitalization 2002→

Idea Stores¹⁵⁶ are a transformation of conventional public libraries into service oriented one-stop information and learning centres – housed in identity creating flagship buildings on the local high street. The most welcoming characteristic is the character of a real customer care and ‘retail feel’. The commercial model is the inspiration here too, albeit the purpose remains to deliver a free, not for profit, public service. The newer ones of the 5 existing ‘Idea Stores’ also incorporate a One Stop Shop - a customer facing service point dealing with local residents’ enquiries relating to housing. Another important factor for the success of Idea Stores, it is that as much effort was put in the concept as on the design of the new buildings.

London Idea store.

Source: http://cdn.ltstatic.com/2005/March/OW142114_942long.jpg

3.5.5 Objective: Social inclusion

¹⁵⁶ <https://www.ideastore.co.uk/> viewed 31/05/2015

With the widening gap between the poor and the rich, accompanied by progressing privatization of public space, socio-spatial segregation becomes more evident and turns very conflictive where it leads to expulsion and gentrification of traditionally low-income neighbourhoods. In urban renewal schemes these processes can always be an unintended side effect and should be avoided at all cost.

Tool: Positive discrimination

Many urban renewal schemes in Europe are specifically targeted to low-income and otherwise disadvantaged (i.e. Sinti or refugee) groups. Under the condition that there are not enough funds to offer all services to the entire population indiscriminately this is a wise strategy – but bears the risk of automatically stigmatizing the population living in the concerned area.

Case Study Scotland Community-led urban renewal^{157, 158}

In 2011, the so called new urban regeneration strategy was launched by the Government of Scotland under the title “Achieving a Sustainable Future” in Scotland is considered a necessary ingredient of economic growth strategies. It is targeted to countries most disadvantaged communities. Reliance on reinforcing endogenous potentials in poor neighbourhood the risk of stigmatization is being reduced.

In 2014, the first 50 community-led organisations have been identified to receive investment of up to £3 million which will support the regeneration of areas throughout Scotland. Of particular interest is the enouncement about a “Investment in a new community capacity building programme. This will focus on areas where there are currently few local organisations, weak networks amongst local people and where local people’s skills and confidence need to be nurtured. It will have a focus on helping people to decide how budgets in their areas are spent”. There are no details yet on how this will work, or who will nominate an area as having low capacity¹⁵⁹.

Kilwinning Town Centre Regeneration Plan (Scotland)

The Main Street is the key open space in Kilwinning and the project aims to transform the historic setting of the Town Centre and the Abbey with high quality,

¹⁵⁷ www.scotland.gov.uk/Resource/Doc/364595/0123891.pdf

¹⁵⁸ <http://www.gov.scot/Topics/Built-Environment/regeneration>

¹⁵⁹ <http://www.communitydevelopmentalliancescotland.org/frontpage/mixed-messages-from-new-regeneration-strategy> seen 8/3/2015

design led public space improvements. The creation of an attractive, robust and adaptable streetscape will encourage the wider regeneration of the town. New paving, seating, lighting and landscaping all contribute to make this a dynamic space that will attract new business, create jobs and increase visitor numbers.

The project was developed in close consultation with the Kilwinning community and key stakeholders over a period of two and a half years and is designed to provide a contemporary streetscape whilst capturing the unique history of the town.

Source:

http://www.urbanrealm.com/buildings/545/Kilwinning_Town_Centre_Regeneration_Plan.html viewed 03/08/2015

3.5.6 Objective: Fighting stigmatization

Stigmatization generally leads to exclusion, but can be stronger than just economic exclusion since it adds other, for example cultural or ethnic prejudices to exclusion. Quite frequently, parts of the disadvantaged or poor population, in order not to admit that they are at the losing end of society, look out for minority groups which they can consider of less value. Sometimes the mere fact of living in a certain neighbourhood can lead to stigmatization. In that case, the objective of urban revalorization scheme may include generating a better image of the neighbourhood.

TOOL: Social engineering

Where an area suffers stigmatization because of the decaying architecture, it may be enough to embark on an uplifting of the facades. If the stigmatization is based on a racial, religious or other personalised argument then physical interventions are not enough. Specific magnets must be found to convince 'respectable' members of society also to move to the area in question as part of the renewal process.

Case study: Rotterdam South Pact¹⁶⁰ 2004

As part of a privatization policy the city of Rotterdam tried to sell part of its renovated housing portfolio in low-income neighbourhoods to prospective home owners, but without much success. For the resident population, mostly migrant, the price was too high and the better off were heading to better zones. In a second attempt it the houses were offered without previous renovation at a minimal cost to self-builders who were obliged to live in the house for certain minimum number of years. These self builders were mostly born Dutch citizens and were widely welcome in the neighbourhood since they were seen as a sign of social upgrading also for themselves. So far, no gentrification has been manifest, but local shops now also include higher value products in their displays.

¹⁶⁰

http://www.innovateballymun.org/sites/default/files/socialinnovation/Social%20Sustainabilityand%20Urban%20Regenerationreport_0.pdf visited 18/05/2015

<p>Working class house in Rotterdam</p> <p>Source: http://static.panoramio.com/photos/large/48500428.jpg</p>	<p>House in South Rotterdam</p> <p>Source: http://global.remax.com/userimages/8/1_4e8637a2c866406586699425cdbba135_ilst.jpg</p>

Case study: Leipzig East Regeneration Area (Germany) ^{161, 162}

Leipzig East encompasses several suburbs to the East of Leipzig's city centre and accommodates a population of 27,000 within an area of 347 ha. This mainly residential area is characterised by dense, late nineteenth-century block structures and large-panel construction development of the 1970s. Historically, the area was known as the 'graphics quarter' due to the dominance of publishing companies and printing works and the residents were mostly 'working class'. During World War II, the area suffered considerable damage, from which the industrial sector never recovered. During the GDR regime only limited resources for reconstruction and maintenance of the built environment were available which led to further physical decay.¹⁶³

Economic decline in East Germany after reunification caused a downturn in housing markets and a movement away from certain neighbourhoods (like the large panel prefabricated housing estates) towards the more affluent parts of the city of Leipzig. In the same way, poorer households moved into the historical Eastern part of Leipzig which recently presents a characteristic of an ageing population, but also families with a high proportion of children and adolescents. Among the less well-off new arrivals we observe a larger number of migrant households and ethnic German immigrants from Eastern Europe. Hence the proportion of migrants in East Leipzig is higher than for the city as a whole. Due to segregation and social disintegration the social structure of East Leipzig

¹⁶¹ Andrea Colantonio and Tim Dixon: 2009. Measuring Socially Sustainable Urban Regeneration in Europe. Oxford Brookes University, Oxford.
http://www.innovateballymun.org/sites/default/files/socialinnovation/Social%20Sustainabilityand%20Urban%20Regenerationreport_0.pdf visited 18/05/2015

¹⁶² <http://www.irs-net.de/download/forschung/5.Statusbericht-Stadtumbau-Ost.pdf> viewed 04/06/2015

¹⁶³ <http://www.leipziger-osten.de/content/stadt-umbauen/ueberblick/> accessed 04/06/2015

- especially the borough of Volkmarisdorf - displays serious problems.

In order to face the evident problems of this area a comprehensive urban regeneration program was started in the 1990s. Soft end land uses were decisive in changing the image of the district. Also the opening of new green spaces (both public and private) as well as cultural events in the district helped considerably and became focal points of community life today.

<p>East Leipzig Source: http://www.leipziger-os-ten.de/typo3temp/pics/b6b8049257.jpg</p>	<p>Living variety in Leipzig Source: http://www.leipziger-os-ten.de/uploads/RTEmagicC_Vielfalt_Leben_web_richtig_txdam2492_022385.jpg.jpg</p>	<p>Leipzig Waldstrasse Source: http://www.stadtbild-deutsch-land.org/forum/index.php?page=Thread&threadID=3712&pageNo=4</p>

With the start of programme implementation, the Leipzig municipality reformed its organisational and management in a three level structure: city-wide administration, an operative district level and participatory neighbourhood levels. Now it is generally accepted that East Leipzig can be considered an example of successful integration. .

Tool: Diversification of housing mix

In the European culture, large and homogeneous housing estates are not liked very much, even by its own residents. People like to be different from others which is expressed, for example, in the desire for an individualized front door. Furthermore, in countries where social housing is not available to everyone any more but only poor families with small or no income, those estates are easily stigmatised. This may extend to the entire neighbourhood if this only consists of similar housing typology. Therefore it is only logical that in order to fight stigmatization, a greater variety of housing types – and status of residents at the same time – is a good answer to the problem.

Case study: Amsterdam Bijlmermeer 1992 & 2007-12^{164, 165}

This large housing estate had become a ghetto of migrants with their associated problems of drug consumption and dealing, general delinquency and unemployment. Physical renovation of the neighbourhood concentrated on partial demolition and a wider mix of housing typology, land uses and tenure variety. This strategy helped to conquer stigmatization of the area and to attract other residents as well, though demanding for higher standards and home ownerships. Social control also helped to reduce the police statistics about criminality. The aspired effect took place, but other critical voices talk about black gentrification.

3.5.7 Objective: Cultural identity

Tool: Participation

The concept of sustainability implies the survival and stable operation of a project after its formal ending – when a project turns into a practice. In urban regeneration this requires that the local population identifies itself with the project which is best achieved through active participation in the planning and decision making right from the beginning. This is part of community building and contributes to the formation of neighbourhood identity.

Case Study Denmark: Copenhagen Kvarterloeft initiative 1997-2007^{166,167,168}

Kvarterloeft was a large scale initiative to revitalize deprived urban areas and to improve their public image through a holistic initiative based on

¹⁶⁴ <http://www.grotestedenbeleid.nl/> ; <http://www.vernieuwdebijlmer.nl/bijlmer11/> seen 24.08.2015

¹⁶⁵ <http://www.amsterdam.nl/wonen-leefomgeving/buurt-bewoner/wijkaanpak/> seen 24.08.2015

¹⁶⁶ http://www.byplanlab.dk/sites/default/files/10_years_of_urban_regeneration.pdf (most complete documentation, seen 8/4/2015

¹⁶⁷ http://webhost.ua.ac.be/ugis/results/udps/DK_kvarterloeft.pdf seen 02/06/2015

¹⁶⁸

http://www.geography.dur.ac.uk/conferences/Urban_Conference/Programme/pdf_files/Annika%20Agger.pdf, visited 02/06/2015

public participation and through public-private partnership. It began in 1997 and concluded in 2007 reaching a total population of about 120,000 people in two types of problematic situation: One were large non-profit housing estates mostly built in the period 1960-80 and the other were older parts of the bigger cities (especially in Copenhagen) with low housing standards, traffic problems or with industrial sites that can be used for new functions.

In the selection of the projects there was an increasing focus on urban competition. Each urban community is positioning itself, striving for growth and attracting residents with strong resources. This not only mirrors global competition trends but also explains the big differences between the goals set up in the plan for each area and the social composition of the same.

An important feature was the institutional set-up and community participation. The funding came from the Dutch government and was administered by the Ministry of Refugees, Immigration and Integration Affairs. Local municipalities identified the quarters and made bids for funding which were granted under the condition that the local authority was providing matching funds. Each scheme had a local operational office staffed by the municipality and supervised by a steering committee of 20 to 25 people representing local bodies and resident initiatives. Public meetings were held regularly and individual projects were prepared by working

groups including the residents.¹⁶⁹

Although it is not easy to change a negative stigma, a survey of the 50 projects shows that the previously negative image of most of the involved neighbourhoods was improved. The conclusion is that participation and transparent processes play important roles. Another survey shows that the Kvarterloeft projects have helped to reduce the scope of vandalism – especially graffiti – and to some extent violence and burglaries in houses. The list of reported program achievements is impressive:¹⁷⁰

- a reduction in the scope of vandalism
- an improvement of residents' perception of each other and the areas
- a strengthening of society cohesion through the formation of traditional societies and networks
- evolution of cross-neighbourhood networks
- a strengthening of social capital in the areas
- development of attractive district plans with residents and experts which have been successfully implemented with a high rate of completion
- the projects were appreciated to be of high quality by residents and experts alike
- successful regeneration of large recreational areas
- increased familiarity with and participation in resident-led initiatives
- a holistic approach has been adopted by various administrations
- involvement of universities in terms of advice, research and publications
- creation of a lively debate about the initiative among professionals
- innovation Danish urban planning practice
- mainstreaming of the kvarterloeft concept in urban renewal legislation and social housing programs
- a new and more user friendly attitude has evolved in the relation between government and local communities.

<p>Maritime Youth house, 95aritime95eft governmental city renewal project, Sundby Harbour, Copenhagen</p>	<p>Community building in the Kvarterloeft urban renewal program Source: http://imaginehorsens.dk/projekter/ord-og-</p>

¹⁶⁹

https://books.google.de/books?id=3sLudUajwTcC&pg=PA48&lpg=PA48&dq=Kvarterloeft&source=bl&ots=OKf_baDdhI&sig=4rdl4i1sGgK5mNsXnPu8y7pkeYU&hl=en&sa=X&ved=0CFUQ6AEwCGoVChMIitDLwYaPxwIVTAYsCh2Srw7#v=onepage&q=Kvarterloeft&f=false seen 8/4/2015

¹⁷⁰ <http://sampac.nl/EUKN2015/www.eukn.org/dsresource9c82.html?objectid=96971> seen 8/4/2015

Source: https://redchalksketch.wordpress.com/2011/04/10/96ari-time-youth-house-denmark-jds-architects/	billeder-konkurrence/
--	-----------------------

3.5.8 Objective: Crime and violence prevention

Over the last years, urban violence has been perceived a problem also in certain European cities – for example in immigrant quarters with high rates of unemployment and in relation to vagrants loitering in public space. Hence, violence reduction and prevention is being frequently included in the list of expected outcomes of urban renewal projects. The three principal strategies in violence reduction and prevention include policing, physical provision and community building.

Tool: Conventional policing

The classical response to deviant behaviour is repression by the state and is still occasionally effective in extreme situation – the main reference case is the strong arm policing initiative promoted by the mayor of New York in the 1990s. A precondition, however, is that the state itself and its police strictly follow democratic principles which is not always the case even in Europe.

*Special security zone declared around a mass housing estate in France.
Source: <http://www.gouvernement.fr/action/les-zones-de-securite-prioritaires-zsp>*

Case Study: France: Zones de Sécurité Prioritaires 2012/13¹⁷¹

Since their introduction in 2012, a total of 80 Priority Security Zones have been declared all over France, with a total population of 1.6 million people.¹⁷² These zones have been chosen according to the concerns of population living within, and the objective is to reduce the levels of delinquency through a concerted action of between the concerned state institutions, and the employment of 500 additional policemen. The targeted forms of delinquency include burglary, violence, drugs, alcohol, underground economies, gatherings of youth in public spaces of housing estates. More recently, prevention of terrorism and drug trafficking has also been included in the argumentation for establishing the ZSPs (Zones de sécurité prioritaire).

¹⁷¹ http://www.liberation.fr/societe/2012/11/15/le-gouvernement-creee-quarante-neuf-zones-de-securite-prioritaires-de-plus_860609 visited last 26/05/2015

¹⁷² <http://www.interieur.gouv.fr/Archives/Archives-des-actualites/2013/ZSP> seen 8/4/2015

First claims of success have been voiced by politicians, like a 32% decrease in reported violence in Amiens, or 28% decrease in the department Gard, but there are contradicting accounts as well.¹⁷³ For example, no information is available whether delinquency has simply displaced to surrounding areas.

<p>Priority Security Zone in Paris. Source: http://referentiel.nouvelobs.com/file/4165929.jpg</p>	<p>Priority Security zone in Amiens, France. Source: http://s2.lemde.fr/image/2012/08/14/534x0/1745922_7_6cf3_la-police-evacue-les-vehicules-incendies_b7c56d1b409fe271fe6a70d67d4b52e9.jpg</p>

TOOL: Shared space streets

Lonely places are often perceived as unsafe, even if there is no statistical evidence to support it. The same applies to streets in which delinquents with cars and motos can escape quickly and easily. On the other hand, a reasonably frequented urban pedestrian area is believed to be relatively safe because there are many potential helpers around who can intervene in case of an attack. Therefore pedestrian areas and traffic speed reduction can reduce the fear of violence and crime.

Case study: Britain, Brighton New Road 2007^{174, 175}

The seaside city of Brighton & Hove on the South coast of England attracts millions of visitors every year. However, over time the historical high street leading from the harbour into the city centre was run down and neglected – most people try get away from it as quick as possible. The Danish landscape planner Jan Gehl was commissioned to redesign the street but did not come up with a standard pedestrian road but proposed a new street typology instead: a shared space between cars (faced with a number of obstacles to reduce their velocity to walking speed) and pedestrians.

The implemented physical improvements – including high quality urban landscaping - significantly increase the frequency of pedestrians and con-

¹⁷³ <http://www.lefigaro.fr/actualite-france/2015/05/12/01016-20150512ARTFIG00316-triste-bilan-pour-les-zsp.php> seen 8/4/2015

¹⁷⁴ <http://gehlarchitects.com/cases/new-road-brighton-uk/> visited 17/05/2015

¹⁷⁵ <http://www.landezine.com/index.php/2011/04/new-road-by-landscape-projects-and-gehl-architects/> visited 30/05/2015

tribute to social control over potential criminal vagrants previously concentrating in this space. Traffic levels have dropped by 93%, the number of pedestrians has increased by 62%, and there has been a 600% increase in 'good' lingering activities. People apparently enjoy being here. Today 86% would like to see more areas like New Road in their city.

Brighton New Road transformed into shared space by the Danish Landscape Architect Jan Gehl

Source: <http://www.landezine.com/wp-content/uploads/2011/04/02-NewRoad-Landscape-project-gehl-architects.jpg>

Tool: Community building and participation

A strong community is the best safeguard against public violence, and when people know each other they are more likely to assist you when threatened by foreigners and intruders. Therefore community building is an effective means of violence prevention and has been introduced in projects where safety is an issue.

Case study Belfast, Northern Ireland^{176,177,178}

Belfast, the capital of Northern Ireland experienced a long history of urban violence. The worst years, locally referred to as 'The Troubles', were

¹⁷⁶ <http://www.northbelfastpartnership.com/images/custom/pageimages/118/4488/people-and-place-mid-term-review.pdf> seen 8/4/2015

¹⁷⁷ <http://sticerd.lse.ac.uk/dps/case/cr/CASereport54.pdf> seen 8/4/2015

¹⁷⁸

https://books.google.de/books?id=DWgeAwAAQBAJ&pg=PA88&lpg=PA88&dq=violence+urban+renewal+belfast&source=bl&ots=_wBtkCtYz3&sig=t9avBmTCZ0tpZPUXqUIX-id-WJJQ&hl=en&sa=X&ved=0CEYQ6AEwBmoVChMI57DSIO2PxiwIVBZdyCh1snQU#v=onepage&q=violence%20urban%20renewal%20belfast&f=false

the period 1969-98, during which over 1,900 citizens were killed while sporadic violent events continued up to 2014.¹⁷⁹ The conflict is said to have evolved between protestants and Catholics – but the thriving interests were rather political than religious.

After ‘the troubles’ were settled in a peace treaty 1998, the ‘URBAN II Community Initiative Programme’ was launched for 2000-2006. A different and complementary program *Neighbourhood Renewal Programme “People and Place”*, was added in 2003. Neighbourhoods in the most deprived 10% of wards across Northern Ireland were identified to possibly being included in the program using a Multiple Deprivation Measure. Following extensive consultation, a total of 36 areas have been included finally in the program, representing a population of approximately 280,000 – or one person in 6 in the country.

The URBAN II Renewal Program¹⁸⁰ must be interpreted in a post-conflict context. The emergence of peace, after nearly three decades of conflict, opens new possibilities especially in areas blighted by fear and violence. Rigid patterns of segregation, increasing territoriality and the growth in the number of interfaces represent the brutal scars of division and mistrust especially in inner North Belfast. The area contains a range of ethno-religious, economic and inner-city problems that characterise its distinctiveness as a place of fear stratified by six peace lines, with the highest rates of deaths during the Troubles and high rates of neighbourhood conflict and intimidation. The area’s problems can be traced back to the mass-movement of the civilian population that followed the outbreak of violence in Northern Ireland in 1969. This left ‘jagged’ edges to ethnic territory, some communities trapped in enclaves and a landscape blighted by rising segregation. Intervening to regenerate and renovate this landscape is one of the key priorities in this operational Programme.

Program activities aimed at combining inner-city change with issues of de-segregation of formerly hostile territories. The URBAN II Programme allowed for visionary responses to: interface areas, contested land blighted by fear and violence, community participation in deeply divided areas, the opportunity to construct cross-community approaches to shared environmental problems, how to rescue and redirect part of the urban economy drifting further and inexorably away from the city fabric, building hope and opportunity for the youth. A priority for URBAN II will be the renewal of the physical environment blighted by economic decline and the legacy of violence. This will include actions to remove the worst environmental eyesores, improve the quality of arterial routes and attractiveness of access points to the area. Specific problems to be addressed include:

- Pervasive sense of fear, danger and direct violence to people and property
- Death and injury, high rates of death and violence

¹⁷⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Belfast#The_Troubles seen 8/4/2015

¹⁸⁰ <http://www.dfpni.gov.uk/urbanop.pdf> seen 8/4/2015

- Land and housing near interface areas blighted by fear, violence and lack of investment confidence
- The Lower North area of Belfast experiences some of the highest rates of physical dereliction, neglect and vandalism. It is fractured by a number of interfaces that have been the scene of recent paramilitary violence and inter-community disturbances.

The Neighbourhood Renewal Strategy “People and Place” was launched in June 2003 and managed through North Belfast Partnership who had been contracted as facilitators the 36 Neighbourhood Renewal Areas (NRAs). Its strategy set out 4 interlinking objectives:

- Community Renewal – to develop confident communities that are able and committed to improving the quality of life in the most deprived neighbourhoods;
- Economic Renewal – to develop economic activity in the most deprived neighbourhoods and connect them to the wider urban economy;
- Social Renewal – to improve the lives of people in the most deprived neighbourhoods through better coordinated services and the creation of safer districts;
- Physical Renewal – to help create attractive, safe, sustainable environments in the most deprived neighbourhoods.

It is interesting to note that two of the seven success indicators were related to violence:

- Number of recorded crimes and offences per 1,000 population.
- Percentage of residents who are afraid to go out alone after dark.

The program is also focusing on delivering Domestic Violence training in the area and has built a link with the local Domestic Violence Unit to look into a more structured Local Community Safety plan. The coordinator has worked in collaboration with local organisations to deliver ‘One Stop Shops’ that run twice a month. These promote education, training services and job opportunities in Belfast to the local residents.

As a concluding remark it should be highlighted that the specific character neither of public violence nor of domestic violence can be resolved through police intervention. Conflict resolution is only conceivable through dialogue and joint personal experiences.

<p>The fencing on the Belfast "peace line". The peace lines were a series of high border barriers in Northern Ireland that separate Irish nationalist and the rest of the country.</p> <p>Source: https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/thumb/0/04/Belfast_peace_line_Cupar_Way.jpg/400px-Belfast_peace_line_Cupar_Way.jpg</p>	<p>Loyalist Mural, Belfast, Northern Ireland, 2012</p> <p>Photo: Marc Gautier . Source: http://farm8.static.flickr.com/7120/7704508126_2d4767f435_m.jpg</p>

3.5.9 Objective: Conviviality, well being

So far, all presented urban renewal activities were designed to support deprived neighbourhoods with serious urban and social problems. Of course, better off parts of the city are also being renewed – usually funded by the ordinary municipal budget – and therefore special programs are not necessary. There are also cheaper since only the physical works need to be financed and the positive long term effects in the sense of place branding are even bigger since international visitors more likely to visit these zones rather than deprived neighbourhoods.

TOOL: Multi-centrality and the enhancement of public open space

Whereas the up-keeping and modernization of individual houses usually are the responsibility of the owner, the valorisation of public and semi-space (smaller streets and places, de-densification of street blocks, attractive public spaces) fall into the responsibility of the municipality. Investments in this field pay back in the long and medium term as quality of life in a city influences the choice of residence for investors, high rank decision makers of companies but also of well-off old age pensioners.

Case Study Italy Bologna: Bella Fuori 2007

In the history of urban renewal Bologna occupies a high popularity since it was the first city in Europe¹⁸¹ which barred the historic centre for individu-

181

<https://books.google.de/books?id=xJHKeXEhn4MC&pg=PA679&lpg=PA679&dq=bologna+traffic+calming&source=bl&ots=2xpx2Ena63&sig=hq1eF1EJmwBM2KMKZUnyYID4xEY&hl=en&sa=X&ved=0CDkQ6AEwBzqUahUKEwi70da4q5DHAhVqnXIKHbrJAeo#v=onepage&q=bologna%20traffic%20calming&f=false> seen 8/4/2015

al motor traffic and kept on refining the system (see chapter **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**).¹⁸² Whereas initial urban regeneration projects centred on the historical precincts of Bologna, a more recent initiative ‘Bella Fuori’^{183, 184, 185} aims at revitalizing peripheral areas of the city, located „outside” the city centre and are a joint venture between the municipality of Bologna and the „Del Monte Foundation” (financing the project). The basic assumption was based on the idea of multi centrality and was to valorise „new urban centralities”. In practice this aim was applied to the rearrangement of the two public garden areas in via Garavaglia: the “Renato Bentivogli” public garden and the new „Francesco Zanardi” civic centre area (2010-12)

<p>Historical centre of Bologna in Italy Source: http://www.energycity2013.eu/media/Results/Bologna/Bologna_02.jpg</p>	<p>Renewal of the Bella Fuori district in Bologna. Source: http://fondazione-delmonte.it/files/documenti/sezioni/progetti/progetti-strategici/bella-fuori/bf-iii-riassunto-percorso-partecipativo-e-immagini.pdf</p>

A second call, in 2012, shifted more away from the initial esthetical approach by addressing the use value of public space (‘commons’) and was started in the neighbourhood San Donato but then spread to different areas with political emphasis on participation setting new rules in the collaborations between the public administrations and citizens in respect to the regeneration of urban commons.

A third phase (2013-15), intended to address eco-ethic dimensions of public space, added ecology as a third dimension in the program.

The three editions of the program well illustrate the global shift in urban renewal priorities: from physical and beautification concerns to public participation and accountability and from there to ecological improvements.

¹⁸²

http://transit.gencat.cat/web.content/articles/arxiu_ponencies_v_congres/giancarlo_sgubbi_experiencia_d_e_la_ciutat_de_bolonya.pdf seen 8/4/2015

¹⁸³ <http://www.comune.bo.it/news/croce-del-biacco-arriva-bella-fuori-30> visited 05/06/2015

¹⁸⁴ <http://fondazione-delmonte.it/progetti/progetti-strategici/bella-fuori> visited 05/06/2015

¹⁸⁵ <http://fondazione-delmonte.it/files/documenti/sezioni/progetti/progetti-strategici/bella-fuori/bf-iii-riassunto-percorso-partecipativo-e-immagini.pdf> viewed 05/06/2015

Another, maybe even more interesting project of the city of Bologna is named 'Competition Autorecuperato'.¹⁸⁶ The idea is that some empty buildings originating from the early 19th century will be leased to a cooperative of self-builders who will renovate the premises under professional guidance and later live in it.

3.5.10 Objective: Heritage conservation

Historic buildings, whether listed or not, account largely for the cultural identity of a city. Furthermore, due to a less competitive land market at their time of origin, the plan could be more generous and the rooms could be higher than modern buildings can afford. Ecologically speaking, the recycling of existing building structures is more sustainable than demolition and new construction anyway.

TOOL: Conversion with change of land use

Listed historic buildings, maybe even with UNESCO certification, are intended to tell us and future generations about our historical past and should therefore be authentic; substantial alterations should be avoided. Conversions, on the contrary, generally maintain the outer skin of a building while the interior can be modified and adjusted to the future occupants need – either residential or commercial.

Case study: Copenhagen: Carlsberg City 2009^{187,188,189}

Revitalization of a listed historical industrial site. The Carlsberg District, the former site of Carlsberg brewery, has been appointed one of Denmark's most important industrial memories with a very important science history. The master plan for the transformation of Carlsberg City District, in 2009, was awarded the prize for 'Best Master Plan in the World' at the World Architecture Festival in Barcelona. The authors of the plan (Entasis) say that they were inspired by the qualities of historic city centres – which is identical as what characterizes the New Urbanism movement.

Once Carlsberg City District is fully developed it will comprise 600,000 square metres of floor space divided into private residences, retail and business premises as well as cultural, sporting and educational venues. The historical buildings only form a small section of the entire development, which softens the elitist character of conservation works. Transport-wise, Carlsberg City District will be well connected by its new modern commuter railway station, "Carlsberg Station", and a new metro station, which is only a few hundred metres from the neighbourhood. Furthermore, a web of bike lanes will provide quick and safe transport for the district's many cyclists.

¹⁸⁶ <http://www.comune.bologna.it/casa/servizi/8:1035/3913/> visited 05/06/2015

¹⁸⁷ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Carlsberg_%28district%29 visited 17/05/2015

¹⁸⁸ <http://www.dac.dk/en/dac-cities/sustainable-cities/all-cases/social-city/carlsberg-our-town/> visited 17/05/2015

¹⁸⁹ <http://www.carlsbergbyen.dk/specials/english-summary/> visited 02/06/2015

Carlsberg City outside Copenhagen – a New Town in former industrial premises.

Source left: [https://s-media-cache-](https://s-media-cache-ak0.pinimg.com/236x/97/df/7c/97df7c176d90f30fb591854f8dfcdb60.jpg)

[ak0.pinimg.com/236x/97/df/7c/97df7c176d90f30fb591854f8dfcdb60.jpg](https://s-media-cache-ak0.pinimg.com/236x/97/df/7c/97df7c176d90f30fb591854f8dfcdb60.jpg)

Source right: <http://www.globalsiteplans.com/files/2012/10/carlsberg.jpg>

4 STANDARDS

Some European countries are more addicted to standards than others. With the DIN Norms Germany was one of the first countries to establish an internationally accepted set of technical norms, but Urban Renewal has to do with people which by definition cannot be classified by a norm. On the other hand certain *standards* can help to guarantee equal rights to all individuals which may become an issue where developers try to enforce urban renewal projects without the consent of the resident population. In the following we will comment only on a small selection of norms to illustrate the spectrum of issues which could benefit from regulation.

4.1 Standards for the selection of renewal areas and beneficiaries

Standards for the selection become necessary in cases where different neighbourhoods or municipalities are competing for public funds and criteria are needed to decide for the allocation of the – always limited – subsidies. Dependent on the political preferences either structural deficits (like physical decay or prevailing sanitary equipment standards) or social indicators (level of unemployment, income or educational levels) are taken into consideration, or a combination of both.

In other cases, the professional quality or expected effectiveness of proposed measures are taken as a base for allocating funds to competing applicants (districts or municipalities). In some cases funding for each case is limited to very few years which allows to reach more and other beneficiaries in a subsequent call.

4.2 Standards for the protection of cultural heritage

In the case of conservation of cultural heritage, the historical importance or architectural values are guiding rules, and the main criteria may be the legal recognition as a cultural monument through the respective agency. However, if the guiding policy intention behind a conservation program was 'place branding' in the first place, authentic conservation may be valued less than touristic appeal and attractiveness for shop owners or hotel managers, and creativity may become more important than authenticity. Coming back to poorer areas, residents in ancient industrial zones may not be very amazed about the idea to reconstruct an authentic early capitalist slum. Their need may be rather to gain a new and positive identity for their neighbourhood which helps to overcome stigmatization and develop civil pride.

In the context of preserving architectural heritage a general trend can be observed on a global scale: Whereas initially only individual buildings (churches, castles, birthplaces of famous personalities) enjoyed legal protection and recognition, nowadays such buildings are seen in its special context and the preservation of cohesive conservation areas has almost become a rule.

Case study: European Charter of the Architectural Heritage 1975¹⁹⁰

¹⁹⁰ Adopted by the Council of Europe, October 1975

The European Charter of the Architectural Heritage has been adopted by the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe and was solemnly proclaimed at the Congress on the European Architectural Heritage held in Amsterdam from 21 to 25 October 1975:

- a) *The European architectural heritage consists not only of our most important monuments: it also includes the groups of lesser buildings in our old towns and characteristic villages in their natural or manmade settings.*
- b) For many years, only major monuments were protected and restored and then without reference to their surroundings. More recently it was realized that, if the surroundings are impaired, even those monuments can lose much of their character.
- c) Today it is recognized that entire groups of buildings, even if they do not include any example of outstanding merit, may have an atmosphere that gives them the quality of works of art, welding different periods and styles into a harmonious whole. Such groups should also be preserved.
- d) The architectural heritage is an expression of history and helps us to understand the relevance of the past to contemporary life.
- e) *The past as embodied in the architectural heritage provides the sort of environment indispensable to a balanced and complete life.*
- f) In the face of a rapidly changing civilization, in which brilliant successes are accompanied by grave perils, people today have an instinctive feeling for the value of this heritage.
- g) This heritage should be passed on to future generations in its authentic state and in all its variety as an essential part of the memory of the human race. Otherwise, part of man's awareness of his own continuity will be destroyed.
- h) *The architectural heritage is a capital of irreplaceable spiritual, cultural, social and economic value.*
- i) Each generation places a different interpretation on the past and derives new inspiration from it. This capital has been built up over the centuries; the destruction of any part of it leaves us poorer since nothing new that we create, however fine, will make good the loss.
- j) Our society now has to husband its resources. Far from being a luxury this heritage is an economic asset which can be used to save community resources.
- k) *The structure of historic centres and sites is conducive to a harmonious social balance.*

By offering the right conditions for the development of a wide range of activities our old towns and villages favoured social integration. They can once again lend themselves to a beneficial spread of activities and to a more satisfactory social mix.

- l) *The architectural heritage has an important part to play in education.*

The architectural heritage provides a wealth of material for explaining and comparing forms and styles and their applications. Today when visual appreciation and first-hand experience play a decisive role in education, it is essential to keep alive the evidence of different periods and their achievements.

The survival of this evidence will be assured only if the need to protect it is understood by the greatest number, particularly by the younger generation who will be its future guardians.

- m) *This heritage is in danger.*

It is threatened by ignorance, obsolescence, deterioration of every kind and neglect. Urban planning can be destructive when authorities yield too readily to economic pressures and to the demands of motor traffic. Misapplied contemporary technology and ill-considered restoration may be disastrous to old structures. Above all, land and property speculation feeds upon all errors and omissions and brings to nought the most carefully laid plans.

- n) *Integrated conservation averts these dangers*

Integrated conservation is achieved by the application of sensitive restoration techniques and the correct choice of appropriate functions. In the course of history the hearts of towns and sometimes villages have been left to deteriorate and have turned into areas of substandard housing. Their deterioration must be undertaken in a spirit of social justice and should not cause the departure of the poorer inhabitants. Because of this, conservation must be one of the first considerations in all urban and regional planning.

It should be noted that integrated conservation does not rule out the introduction of modern architecture into areas containing old buildings provided that the existing context, proportions, forms, sizes and scale are fully respected and traditional materials are used.

- o) *Integrated conservation depends on legal, administrative, financial and technical support.*

- **Legal.** Integrated conservation should make full use of all existing laws and regulations that can contribute to the protection and preservation of the architectural heritage. Where such laws and regulations are insufficient for the purpose they should be supplemented by appropriate legal instruments at national, regional and local levels.
- **Administrative.** In order to carry out a policy of integrated conservation, properly staffed administrative services should be established.
- **Financial.** Where necessary the maintenance and restoration of the architectural heritage and individual parts thereof should be encouraged by suitable forms of financial aid and incentives, including tax measures. It is essential that the financial resources made available by public authorities for the restoration of historic centres should be at least equal to those allocated for new construction.

- **Technical.** There are today too few architects, technicians of all kinds, specialized firms and skilled craftsmen to respond to all the needs of restoration.. It is necessary to develop training facilities and increase prospects of employment for the relevant managerial, technical and manual skills. The building industry should be urged to adapt itself to these needs. Traditional crafts should be fostered rather than allowed to die out.

- p) *Integrated conservation cannot succeed without the cooperation of all.*
- q) Although the architectural heritage belongs to everyone, each of its parts is nevertheless at the mercy of any individual.
- r) The public should be properly informed because citizens are entitled to participate in decisions affecting their environment. Each generation has only a life interest in this heritage and is responsible for passing it on to future generations.
- s) *The european architectural heritage is the common property of our continent.*

Conservation problems are not peculiar to any one country. They are common to the whole of Europe and should be dealt with in a coordinated manner. It lies with the Council of Europe to ensure that member states pursue coherent policies in a spirit of solidarity.

4.3 Standards for energy conservation

With the pressing concern for CO₂ reduction and mitigation of Climate Change there is a new political will to enforce adequate standards in that direction. In Europe space heating is the most important energy consumer in the built environment and therefore standards have been introduced first to measure the insulation quality of the building skin and their components. However, as the entire energy demand for a building depends on many factors, including for example also the size and shape of a building, or the efficiency and energy source of a heating system it has become mandatory in Germany, for example, that suppliers of housing provide an energy passport for each dwelling. At least in theory, as the energy demand boils down to operation costs of the dwelling, it is assumed that the higher demand for energy efficient buildings induces the house builders to increase the energy standards of their product.

Even if two houses look very much the same, they can be valued much differently according to their energy saving standards: Two houses in a German renewal area, one (on the left) before and the other (on the right) after energetic retrofitting. In fact, the requirement of preserving the architectural appearance while improving the energy performance can be an important, and often very expensive, requirement which justifies public subsidies for urban renewal.

Photos: *Florian Steinberg*

4.4 Standards for ecological buildings

In many countries the environmental qualities – which in fact should be larger than just the energy demand and can include the expected lifetime of a building, the ecological qualities etc.– are of interest for the construction industry as a selling argument. They have been pushing for a certification system ('labelling') in many countries referring to the British „BREEAM“ (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method) or the US Green Building Council based „LEED“ (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design, 1995) or the „MINERGIE-ECO“ label for public buildings and multi-family buildings in Switzerland. Germany, which is known for certain perfectionist tendencies, has developed a set of more demanding standards with about 65 different measurable criteria including for example also ecological, economic, socio-cultural, location, technical and process oriented criteria.¹⁹¹

In this documentation we just intend to demonstrate the variety standards and their different criteria. The housing-construction toolbox will provide more specific information in this respect.

¹⁹¹ Jörg Dettmar. Der deutsche Ansatz zur Zertifizierung der Nachhaltigkeit von Gebäuden – das Risiko der Quantifizierung. TRIALOG 97: 45-48. www.trialog-journal.de

5 TECHNOLOGIES AND PRODUCTS

Technologies and products applied in urban renewal mostly refer to building construction and infrastructure provision – both of them are being dealt with to considerable detail in other EC-Link Tool Boxes. Therefore in this section we will only refer to certain principles which repeatedly are being discussed in the context of urban renewal and urban revitalization.

5.1 Energy saving for appliances

Energy efficiency of electrical and other power appliances has fortunately improved considerably over the past couple of decades, like in the case of LED lamps just to name an example. It remains important, however, not to forget zero energy *design elements* in the buildings, such as natural lighting for bathrooms and kitchen and cross ventilation to reduce the need for air conditioning at least for part of the year.

5.2 Passive energy conservation / Passive or Solar houses^{192, 193}

The original concept of passive energy use refers to capturing environmental heat and cooling gains just through adequate design and positioning – in contrast to active heating -- through ovens or cooling by use of air conditioning.

Passive houses were first introduced in Germany and in Scandinavia from 1990 onwards, but today the concept is known and applied all over the world. Its characteristics are very high energy saving standards, requiring only 10% of typical energy demand compared to customary construction. For example, In the UK, an average new house built to the Passive House standard would use 77% less energy for space heating, compared to the circa-2006 Building Regulations.¹⁹⁴ Primary energy demand for heating, warm water and electricity must not be more than 120 kWh/m² per year (37900 btu). This is normally achieved through hyper insulation and heat recovery for air exchange.

<p>Passive Energy house in Darmstadt, Germany. Info: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Passive_house. Photo: Kosta Mathéy</p>	<p>Passive house technology. Source: Passive house institute. Darmstadt, Germany</p>

¹⁹² <http://passipedia.org/basics> seen 18/08/2015;

¹⁹³ <http://passiv.de/en/> ; <http://www.passivhausprojekte.de/index.php?lang=en>; both seen 18/08/2015;

¹⁹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Passive_house seen 18/08/2015

5.3 Active energy conservation

The concept of active energy use in housing relies on in-house energy generation instead of relying on the grid or non-renewable energy resources. In the case of a zero energy house all energy needed for the operation and use of a house are self produced, whereas a Plus Energy house produces extra energy which can be used for productive activities or fed into the grid. However, in none of these house building concepts the incorporated energy during construction is being accounted for, nor is there a single authority providing a universal definition. On the contrary, there are numerous persons or institutions claiming authorship of the concept.

5.3.1 Zero energy house

The concept of the zero energy house goes back to Alexander Pike and some other scholars working at Cambridge University in the UK in the 1970s. They called it the 'Autonomous House'¹⁹⁵ and extended it also to other means of self-sufficiency apart from energy.

Modern zero energy houses mostly incorporate large areas of photovoltaic panels apart from possibly other energy generating appliances and feed electric energy into the grid during daytime, which they recover back during the night, when there is no sunlight to produce home energy.

<p><i>A Zero Energy house in Germany. Note the large roof area covered by photo voltaic cells. Source: http://www.epbd-ca.eu/themes/nearly-zero-energy</i></p>	<p><i>The first concept of a Zero Energy house in Cambridge, UK, 1975</i></p>

5.3.2 Energy Plus houses

Finally, a Plus Energy house is designed to use more energy than it would use up in a 24-hour cycle. The surplus can be used, for example, to charge the batteries of an electric car, which is the case of the demonstration energy plus house built by the German Government in Berlin, 2011.¹⁹⁶

¹⁹⁵ Vale, Brenda and Robert, The Autonomous House. Thames & Hudson, 1975.

¹⁹⁶ <http://www.buildup.eu/cases/40001> seen 18/08/2015

<p>Efficiency House Plus. In Berlin Photo: Schwarz (BMVBS)</p>	<p>Energy Plus apartment building in Frankfurt Source 'Wege-zum-Effizienzhaus-Plus'. MBVBS, Germany</p>

There are a number of means how to achieve an energy+ performance and which combine two complementary strategies:¹⁹⁷

- a) Create an energy-efficient building:
 - Design a compact building
 - Optimum orientation
 - Thermal zoning
 - Thermal insulation
 - “Super windows”
 - Avoid thermal bridging
 - Airtightness
 - Screens to depict behaviour visually
 - Low system temperature
 - Short pipe runs
 - Hydronic balancing
 - Efficient operating systems
 - Demand-controlled systems
 - Efficient appliances
 - Efficient lighting
 - Heat recovery
- b) Use renewable energy
 - Solar gains through the windows
 - Use daylight
 - Solar collectors
 - Biogenic fuels
 - Geothermal or ambient heat
 - Heat recovery
 - Photovoltaics
 - Wind turbines

The following graph shows the achievements in energy saving housing in Germany

¹⁹⁷ http://www.ibp.fraunhofer.de/content/dam/ibp/en/documents/Areas-of-Expertise/heat-technology/2014-08_Broschuere_Wege-zum-Effizienzhaus-Plus_engl.pdf. Page 10. Seen 18/08/2015

5.4 Decentralized energy generation

This topic directly relates to the precedent paragraph as long as we are concerned with individual building. Eventually we could conceive a city of 100,000 houses as a concentration of 100,000 small scale and sustainable power stations – and stop worrying about climate change in the future. Nevertheless, more efficient are combined district power-heating (or: cooling) plants. These already form part of many urban renewal projects in Europe.

As cities tend to grow rapidly, we may find it more sensitive to break down not only administration but also technical infrastructures in smaller decentralized units. Local needs can be better catered for, and transmission losses cut to a minimum.

6 INDICATORS AND VERIFICATION METHODOLOGIES

Urban renewal programs are mostly promoted in the shape of a larger or regional development program or project funded through public funds. In the field of international cooperation, a good program design should be clear about its objectives and provide milestones at which the achievements of the project can be evaluated and the strategy adjusted, if needed. In municipal urban renewal projects such evaluation is rarely projected and budgeted for, and the only proof of success in that case is the fact that the funds have been disbursed in time. This of course does not tell anything about quality of sustainability.

Therefore some more meaningful evaluation and adjustment mechanisms should be built into any funding program for urban renewal projects. In most international organizations some variation of the *Logical Frame Analysis*¹⁹⁸ has been maintained, which is a very useful instrument to design and later on to follow up the success of a project. In Germany, the GIZ had developed a more sophisticated version of the same principle and named it 'Project Oriented Project Planning' (ZOPP).¹⁹⁹ After some years they discovered that the focus just on planning is not good enough, since project execution and evaluation require similarly rigorous quality standards. This why they went a step further and introduced Project Cycle Management (CPM)^{200,201} as an adequate methodology to guide projects from beginning to end. Most other European countries' cooperation agencies also use similar though less detailed quality control methodologies.

6.1 Criteria and Indicators for the selection of a renewal area:

When it comes to urban renewal projects the first initiative may come from the municipality or district concerned in which case only the individual beneficiaries may require a fair selection process. In Europe, most urban renewal projects belong to programs with more than one project and which is partially funded by the central or provincial government. In that case there must exist clear criteria for the selection of benefitting neighbourhoods, and indicators may become necessary where the criteria cannot easily be measured – like in the case of 'disadvantaged neighbourhoods'

Example: Kvarter Loeft Program in Denmark (see chapter 3.5.7)

The indicators in the map are of both physical and social character:

With respect to **physical indicators**, the map can identify/analyse the areas with a high proportion of:

- *small flats (under 60 m²)*
- *flats which lack basic installations (toilet/bath/central heating)*
- *residents who live in few m²*

With respect to **socio-economic indicators**, the map identified the areas with a high proportion of:

¹⁹⁸ <http://www.evropa.gov.rs/Evropa/ShowDocument.aspx?Type=Home&Id=525> visited 24/08/2015

¹⁹⁹ <http://web.mit.edu/urbanupgrading/upgrading/issues-tools/tools/ZOPP.html> visited 24/08/2015

²⁰⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/project-and-programme-cycle-management-guidance_en visited 24/08/2015

²⁰¹ http://www.cfcu.gov.tr/spos/tools/pcm_training_handbook.pdf visited 24/08/2015

- *residents outside the workforce*
- *residents with a short educational background*
- *residents with a short educational background*
- *residents with low incomes*

6.2 Indicators for success of renewal measures

Once all the objectives of a program have been decided upon it makes sense to be able to confirm and measure whether these have been achieved at the end of a program – or even better already during the process so that corrective measures can be taken in the process. Therefore each objective must be associated with one or several indicators which can be quantified and are easily verifiable. For that purpose, also the sources for verification need to be defined at the same time.

Example: Belfast success indicators for urban renewal.²⁰²

Most important Outcome Indicators include:

- Number and percentage of population of working age who are registered unemployed,
- Economically inactive and in workless households.
- Levels of qualifications in the adult population.
- School examination attainment figures.
- Standardised Mortality Rates (by sex and age).
- Number and percentage of disabled, incapacitated and long-term sick.
- Number of recorded crimes and offences per 1000 population.
- Percentage of residents who are afraid to go out alone after dark.

7 SOME LESSONS LEARNT

7.1 Participation and PPP

In order to become sustainable, urban infrastructure and public space improvements require regular care and maintenance beyond the day inauguration. In most cases, the local authorities are unable to guarantee this service all over the city to the same extent. Furthermore, many urban renewal projects require some residents or business to be re-located which creates great dissatisfaction unless a fair and reasonable solution can be negotiated between the different stakeholders. In the same way care and maintenance by the community can only be achieved if the same is already involved in the planning phase and can identify themselves with the renewal outcome. Certainly, participation takes more time than top-down decisions but helps to overcome civic resistance and brings political rewards to the decision makers.

7.2 Need for subsidies

The reason why a neighbourhood slip into a state of disrepair and show certain social difficulties is the lack of investment capacity – either by the local authority or by the resi-

²⁰² <http://www.northbelfastpartnership.com/images/custom/pageimages/118/4488/people-and-place-mid-term-review.pdf> seen 8/4/2015

dents. Therefore almost all European urban renewal and revitalization projects involve public funding to a certain degree. A 100% funding is almost never achieved and often not wanted in order to encourage the participation of the beneficiaries' right from the beginning. It has also been observed that in general public source infrastructure and services improvement encourage private house owners – which are the rule in Europe – to invest in parallel.

7.3 Neighbourhood contracts

In Europe politicians are sometimes over optimistic in their declarations and executing administrative agencies are not always very eager to engage in tasks that fall outside their day-to-day routine. Or, on the other hand, once they have accustomed themselves to work with public funding they expect the availability of such funding to continue forever and do not feel any stimulation to push for early completion of a renewal program. Therefore some governments have integrated mutually binding contractual obligations in urban renewal programs. A good example are the '*Contrats de Quartier*' in Brussels or in different cities in Switzerland.^{203, 204} Another interpretation of the concept are the Green Contacts in Murcia, Spain,²⁰⁵ for fighting climate change or the public - private partnership programme ECOPROFIT in Graz, Austria to stimulate private business investments (see case study in section 3.1.3)

Example for Neighbourhood contracts in Brussels, Belgium^{206, 207}

Belgium has a large number of run down urban quarters and was searching for transparent and fair mechanism to achieve visible results in short time while reaching the maximum number of neighbourhoods.

Their response were the so called Neighbourhood Contracts between the provincial government and the local authorities and were in operation between 1994 and 2008 (after that they were replaced by Sustainable Neighbourhood contracts which added a focus on ecological improvement).^{208, 209, 210} The program was extremely flexible to adapt to local conditions; therefore instead of rigidly fixing the type of eligible investments the purpose was negotiated in detail between the government and local administration, with the results documented in a contract. In that period 52 neighbourhood improvement programs were executed and funded with about 10 Million Euros each, to which the local authorities contributed another 10% to 30% from their own funds. More than half of the sum was invested in housing construction and improvements.

²⁰³ <http://www.ville-geneve.ch/themes/social/action-proximite/contrats-quartier/> visited 19/08/2015

²⁰⁴ <http://www.lausanne.ch/thematiques/vivre-a-lausanne/residents/vie-de-quartier/contrats-de-quartier.html> visited 19/08/2015

²⁰⁵ http://mirror.unhabitat.org/bp/bp.list.details.aspx?bp_id=1075 reviewed 23/05/2015

²⁰⁶ <http://be.brussels/living-in-brussels/urban-development/urban-renewal/neighbourhood-revitalisation-projects> visited 19/08/2015

²⁰⁷ <http://www.bruxelles.be/artdet.cfm/4962> visited 19/08/2015

²⁰⁸ <http://www.sustainablecity.be/brusselsgreencapital/case-stories/sustainable-neighbourhood-contract-masui?context=42> visited 19/08/2015

²⁰⁹ <http://www.sustainablecity.be/brusselsgreencapital/case-stories/sustainable-neighbourhood-contract-canal-midi?context=32> visited 19/08/2015

²¹⁰ <http://www.quartiers.irisnet.be/> visited 19/08/2015

The Neighbourhood Contracts all aim at integrated quarter development. They address the creation and renovation of housing, public buildings and spaces, but also include socio-economic actions or infrastructure and services (social, cultural, sporting and others), at the level of the local district. Public participation is mandatory. Above all, they were supported by a partnership between public authorities (local and regional), private partners, investors, NGOs and the inhabitants of the areas in question. The Neighbourhood Contracts comprise three clearly defined different stages:

- a) The preparation stage, lasting nine months, during which the programme is drawn up by the local authority or the research bureau selected;
- b) The implementation of the programme, lasting four years;
- c) A possible extension of two years for rounding off the last projects.

A programme is designed by a consultant under the supervision of the local authority for each Neighbourhood Contract. All individual Neighbourhood Contract programmes must be executed over a maximum period of four years (with a possible extension of two years to complete the last projects). The definition of a maximum length of funding was intended to discipline slow public administrations and to reach a larger number of communities.

7.4 Risk of gentrification and expulsion

In Europe many people prefer to live in a central or historic part of the city and if such a zone is being upgraded as part of an urban revitalization program. Higher income citizens move in and replace poorer sections of society who cannot compete in a liberal housing market. This process is known as Gentrification²¹¹ and has been observed in many parts of the world. This is a real danger in urban renewal programs. The example of the Brussels neighbourhood contracts is an important reference of how to avoid gentrification through positive discrimination, integrated social development and a coverage over many low-income neighbourhoods in the first place.

11 social housing units and a kindergarden were built as part of the Neighbourhood Contract in Ixelles, Belgium

Source:

[http://www.r2d2architecture.be/images/Projects/256_BR OCHET/256%20\(3\).jpg](http://www.r2d2architecture.be/images/Projects/256_BR OCHET/256%20(3).jpg)

The redeveloped Marseille docks were inaugurated in 2015. The project transforms the 19th century warehouses that surround the port into a social, cultural and commercial space with upper class housing in the upper floors.

<http://www.abitare.it/en/habitat-en/urban-design->

²¹¹ <http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/gentrification> visited 24/08/2015

On the other hand, private initiative can sometimes get interested in the rehabilitation of historic factory buildings and invest to a higher standard than public programs can do. Examples include The Carlsberg City (see case study in chapter 3.5.10) is one example; another would be part of the old Port in Marseille, France where one defunct warehouse is being converted into luxury flats and commerce.